

6G MULTiband Wireless and Optical Signalling for Integrated
CommunicAtions, Sensing and Localisation

D4.1 “Network and Carrier Synchronisation Techniques”

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Executive Summary

6G-MUSICAL, a pioneering project under the European Commission's (EC) SNS JU (Smart Network Services Joint Undertaking), is redefining wireless services by seamlessly integrating radar functionality into next-generation wireless communication systems. The project focuses on equipping edge nodes with advanced Radio Frequencies (RF)/radar-based radio-sensing capabilities that operate in harmony with communication components. These integrated systems will enable precise localisation, object tracking, and 3D imaging with accuracy and resolution reaching centimetre-level. 6G-MUSICAL also aims to explore innovative system architectures and signal designs that are both spectrally and energy-efficient, facilitating high-rate communication across multiple frequency bands while ensuring accurate sensing and localisation.

The project distinguishes itself from other joint communication and sensing research in two key aspects. Firstly, in addition to non-connected objects for sensing, it considers the connected objects, addressing the growing trend towards universal connectivity. Secondly, it tackles the critical challenge of synchronisation among edge nodes by leveraging a combination of optical and electronic technologies to generate precise and stable reference signals. This breakthrough will enable a network of smart, cooperative multistatic radars for ultra-accurate localisation and high-resolution 3D object reconstruction within future 6G systems.

In the wireless domain, the project will define new waveforms suitable for radio-sensing and communications, exploit compressive sensing techniques, and develop cooperative multimode sensing and localisation algorithms. In the network domain, key activities will relate to procedures for synchronisation/calibration among edge nodes, compression techniques to enable low-overhead transport of sensing data to a fusion centre, and multistatic sensing algorithms. The optical and electrical technologies will develop and distribute reference signals, as well as create novel antennas, to address the requirements of 6G. Machine learning (ML) will be used to optimise the system and services jointly. Key technologies will be demonstrated in laboratories to meet a stringent set of predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). There are seven WPs in 6G-MUSICAL, each covering specific objectives of the project.

Work Package (WP) 4, titled "Network Synchronisation, Cloud Radio Sensing and Resource Allocation," encompasses four Tasks (T4.1–T4.4), which collectively contribute to achieving and addressing three objectives of the 6G-MUSICAL project:

- Objective 3 (design and develop low-noise and highly stable reference sources for RF carrier and timing synchronisation)
- Objective 4 (develop and validate cooperative MIMO multistatic sensing algorithms to enable high-accuracy localisation, tracking, and high-resolution 3D imaging).
- Objective 5 (develop dynamic resource allocation schemes to optimise radio resources for localisation, sensing, and communication requirements).

This deliverable, D4.1, focuses on activities within T4.1 and T4.2 and presents initial results on:

1. Definition of clustering schemes to form Tx/Rx pairs for multistatic sensing;
2. Developing cooperative sensing algorithms;
3. Performance evaluation of reduced information exchange and impact of non-perfect synchronisation;

4. Wireless self-synchronisation algorithms;
5. Generation and distribution of precise clock and carrier frequency for synchronisation among network nodes.

The outcome of T4.1 and T4.2 will play a crucial role in the success of 6G-MUSICAL, as synchronisation across network nodes is essential for enabling multi-node sensing capabilities, including accurate localisation and object identification.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Form
AP	Access Point
AFDM	Affine Frequency Division Multiplexing
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIM	Application Interface Module
AoA	Angle of Arrival
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
BER	Bit Error Rate
BPF	Bandpass Filter
BS	Base Station
BSM	Bistatic Signal Matching
CA	Carrier Aggregation
CC	Cross Correlation
CF	Cell-Free
CFO	Carrier Frequency Offset
CIM	Communication Interface Module
CoMP	Coordinated Multipoint
CP	Cyclic Prefix
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRB	Cramér-Rao bound
CU	Central Unit
CUT	Coordinated Universal Time
DC	Dual Connectivity
DCM	Dispersion Compensation Module
DFRC	Dual-Functional Radar-Communication
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
D-JCAS	Distributed Joint Communication and Sensing
DL	Downlink
DOA	Direction of Arrival
DoF	Degree-of-Freedom
DU	Distributed Unit
EDFA	Erbium Doped Fibre Amplifier
EML	Externally Modulated Laser
EO	Electro-optic
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
IDFT	Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform
ISI	Inter-symbol Interference
JCAS	Joint Communication and Sensing
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LoS	Line-of-Sight
LPF	Low Pass Filter
MAC	Medium Access Control

MF	Matched Filter
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLE	Maximum Likelihood Estimator
MLL	Mode-locked Laser
MP	Matrix Pencil
MRTD	Maximum Relative Timing Difference
MZM	Mach-Zehnder modulator
NCD	Network Configuration Database
NLoS	Non-Line-of-Sight
NRZ	Non-return-to-zero
OBPF	Optical Bandpass Filter
OFC	Optical Frequency Comb
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
OOK	On-off-keying
OR	Offset Reciprocity
OTFS	Orthogonal Time Frequency Space
PD	Photodiode
PLL	Phase-Locked Loop
PMCW	Phase Modulated Continuous Wave
PMod	Phase Modulator
PON	Passive Optical Network
PRBS	Pseudorandom Binary Sequences
PSD	Power Spectral Density
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAD	Resource Availability Database
RBW	Resolution Bandwidth
RCS	Radar Cross Section
RD	Range-Doppler
RF	Radio Frequency
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RU	Remote Unit
SA	Serving Area
SCIM	Sensing Clustering Interface Manager
SFDR	Spurious-free Dynamic Range
SFO	Sampling Frequency Offset
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SNS JU	Smart Network Services Joint Undertaking
SSB	Single-Sideband
SSMF	Standard Single Mode Fibre
Sync-E	Synchronous Ethernet
TAE	Timing Misalignment
TDD	Time Division Duplex
TDOA	Time-difference-of-arrival
TO	Time Offset
TOA	Time-of-Arrival
UDN	Ultra-Dense Network

UE	User equipment
UL	Uplink
ULA	Uniform Linear Array
VOA	Variable Optical Attenuator
WDM	Wavelength Division Multiplexing
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project

1 Introduction

WP4 of the 6G-MUSICAL project is dedicated to developing key mechanisms and algorithms to enable multistatic sensing and localisation in a cell-free network environment. Specifically, it addresses time-frequency synchronisation among nodes, which is an essential requirement for effective multistatic sensing, as well as algorithms for joint processing of sensing data across different nodes. Additionally, WP4 focuses on optimising resource allocation to enhance sensing and localisation capabilities. This deliverable encompasses Tasks 4.1 and 4.2, which lay the foundation for the technical framework of multistatic sensing. These tasks focus on defining criteria for node selection, designing advanced joint processing algorithms, and establishing network synchronisation mechanisms.

Task 4.1, “Multi-Node Sensing and Synchronisation Mechanisms”, is led by IMEC with the participation of IT and UCL. This task focuses on exploring bistatic and multistatic sensing architectures and algorithms for detecting, localising, and tracking connected and passive objects, while addressing stringent synchronisation requirements. It will evaluate the performance of these sensing schemes against monostatic sensing, develop a detailed multistatic architecture, and conduct four key activities:

- i. Defining clustering schemes for transmitter-receiver pairs to support a cell-free, evolutive architecture with functional splitting and varying synchronisation accuracy;
- ii. Designing joint processing algorithms that optimise information exchange and compression;
- iii. Performing sensitivity analysis to assess the impact of reduced information exchange and imperfect synchronisation;
- iv. Developing wireless self-synchronisation algorithms for nodes with no access to wired synchronisation due to geographical limitations or in case of disruption of the fronthaul.

Task 4.2, “Node Precise Clock and Low Noise Carrier Frequency Synchronisation”, is led by UCL with contributions from IT and MEN. This task aims to achieve sub-10-ps clock precision and sub-200-fs jitter RF/mm carrier frequency synchronisation for wireless edge nodes using point-to-multipoint networks, such as radio access network (RAN) and passive optical networks (PON), with commercial transceivers. It involves developing narrow-band filtering and control algorithms to ensure low-phase noise and high-power carrier frequency signals over long distances without dispersion-induced fading. Sub-10-ps clock synchronisation will leverage clock phase caching techniques, optimising caching rates, measuring fibre time-of-flight changes, and designing MAC layer protocols for simultaneous data and clock synchronisation. To scale over 1000 nodes, optical and electrical amplification techniques will be optimised, including low-noise optical amplifiers for large splits. High isolation between clock and data signals will be achieved through phase/delay locking circuits and specialised filtering mechanisms, ensuring precise, scalable, and cost-effective synchronisation.

1.1 Organisation of the Document

The document is organised as follows, starting with the definition of essential terms in **Section 2**.

Section 3 outlines synchronisation requirements for multistatic sensing to achieve KPIs defined in WP2.

Section 4 introduces clustering criteria for nodes based on sensing needs, capabilities, and spatial positions.

Section 5 examines cooperative sensing algorithms, comparing performance under full and reduced information sharing to alleviate fronthaul link load.

Section 6 explores wireless self-synchronisation techniques, including channel reciprocity and angle-

of-arrival methods, for cases where fronthaul-based synchronisation is unavailable.

Section 7 presents advanced optical technologies for generating and distributing precise clock and carrier frequency signals, integrated with electronic modules in the nodes. A unified solution for ps-level clock synchronisation and phase-synchronized RF carrier generation is proposed and experimentally demonstrated.

Section 8 is the conclusion of this document.

2 Definitions

This section introduces essential definitions to support the technical discussions throughout this report. The definitions are divided into network-related and synchronisation-related categories.

2.1 Network-Related Definitions

This subsection defines important terms relevant to the sensing and communication systems addressed in this report. Specifically, the following definitions are divided into sensing, communication, and joint sensing-communication categories, respectively.

2.1.1 Sensing Related Definitions

- **Definitions of the different types of sensing**

In this document the term sensing refers to radio-based sensing (also called Radar) where changes in the received radio waves are analysed for range, speed, angle, and shape of an object exposed to the radio waves. Radar systems are distinguished by the geometric arrangement of their transmit and receive components, namely, monostatic, bistatic, Quasi-monostatic, and multistatic configurations. The details are outlined in deliverable D2.2 of 6G-MUSICAL, and here we only review the main concept.

In a monostatic radar, the transmitter and receiver are co-located and often share a standard antenna. In contrast, bistatic radar features spatially separated transmitter and receiver units, with baseline distances (physical separation between the transmitter and receiver) often comparable to the target range. Quasi-monostatic radar is a special case of bistatic radar with a small baseline that approximates monostatic geometries while enabling flexible deployment on platforms such as vehicular edge devices. A multistatic radar comprises multiple transmitters and receivers distributed across different locations, enabling enhanced coverage, improved detection, and resilience to interference and jamming.

- **Model-related definitions**

- Clutter: Unwanted echoes originating from non-target objects in the environment that degrade the quality or interpretation of the desired sensing signal.
- Radar cross section (RCS): A measure of how much electromagnetic energy an object reflects, which is determined by its size, shape, orientation, and material properties.
- Delay: The time it takes for a signal to travel from transmitter to receiver via a specific path.
- Doppler (shift): The frequency shift caused by the relative motion between the transmitter, target, and receiver.
- Angle: The direction of arrival (DOA) or departure of a signal, typically described by azimuth and elevation.

- **Processing-related definitions**

- Coherent processing: Signal processing that exploits phase information to enable accurate parameter estimation.
- Non-coherent processing: Signal processing that relies only on amplitude or power, discarding phase information.
- Resolution: The minimum separation in time, frequency, or space that a system can distinguish between two targets.

- Accuracy: The degree of closeness between the estimated value and the ground truth of a parameter, such as range and velocity.
- Integration time: The time interval over which received signals are combined to improve detection or estimation performance.
- **Metric definitions**
 - Root mean square error (RMSE): A measure of estimation error that represents the average magnitude of the deviations between estimated and actual values.
 - Probability of detection: The probability that a system correctly detects a target, defined as the ratio of accurate detections to the total number of actual targets.
 - Probability of false alarm: The probability that a system declares the presence of a target when no target is present.
 - Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR): The ratio of signal power to noise power, which influences detection and estimation performance.
 - Cramér-Rao bound (CRB): A theoretical lower bound on the variance of any unbiased estimator, used to benchmark estimation accuracy.
 - Computational complexity: An estimate of the resources—typically time or operations—required to execute an algorithm.

2.1.2 *Communications Related Definitions*

- **Architecture-related definitions**
 - Centralized architecture: An architecture where a central node handles the signal processing, and decision-making.
 - Distributed architecture: An architecture where processing tasks are shared among multiple nodes, each handling part of the computation based on locally available data.
 - Edge computing: A paradigm where computation is performed at or near the data source (e.g., sensor nodes or edge devices) to reduce latency and fronthaul requirements.
 - Cloud computing: A computing paradigm where processing and storage are performed in remote, large-scale data centres.
 - Functional splitting: The partitioning of network functions between centralized and distributed units (DUs) in a RAN, allowing trade-offs between latency, fronthaul capacity, and processing complexity.
- **Model-related definitions**
 - Channel model: A mathematical representation of the physical propagation environment, which models how signals are affected by fading, path loss, delay, and interference.
 - Uplink (UL): The communication link from a user device (e.g., UE) to an access point (AP).
 - Downlink (DL): The communication link between an AP and a user device.
 - Multipath propagation: A phenomenon where transmitted signals arrive at the receiver via multiple paths due to reflections, scattering, and diffraction, often causing fading and inter-symbol interference (ISI).
 - Line-of-Sight (LoS) / Non-Line-of-Sight (NLoS): LoS refers to direct signal propagation

without obstructions, while NLoS involves indirect paths due to obstructions, scatterers or reflections.

- **Processing-related definitions**

- Linear processing: Signal processing methods that apply linear operations, such as filtering or combining, to enhance signal quality or extract information.
- Non-linear processing: Methods that involve non-linear operations (e.g., thresholding, decision feedback), often used in detection, decoding, or interference cancellation.
- Digital processing: Processing of signals in the digital domain, typically after analogue-to-digital conversion, enabling flexible and programmable operations.
- Analog processing: Continuous-time processing using circuits, RF waveguide, or microwave photonics methods.
- Hybrid processing: A combination of analogue and digital processing, commonly used in massive MIMO systems to reduce hardware complexity while retaining beamforming flexibility.
- Beamforming: A signal processing technique used to control the directionality of signal transmission or reception by adjusting the phase and amplitude across multiple antennas.

- **Metric definition**

- Bit error rate (BER): The ratio of incorrectly received bits to the total number of transmitted bits, used to evaluate communication reliability.
- Capacity: The theoretical maximum data rate of a communication channel under given bandwidth and SNR conditions, typically measured in bits/s.
- Probability of outage: The likelihood that the communication system's performance (e.g., SNR or data rate) falls below a predefined threshold.
- Latency: The total time delay from transmission to reception, including processing, queuing, and propagation delays.
- Throughput: The rate at which useful data is successfully transmitted over a communication channel, usually measured in bits per second.
- Spectral efficiency: The amount of information transmitted per unit of bandwidth, expressed in bits/s/Hz, representing efficient use of spectral resources.
- Energy efficiency: The amount of energy consumed per successfully transmitted bit, often measured in Joules/bit.

2.1.3 Joint Sensing and Communication Definitions

- **Radar-Communication Coexistence:**

- A paradigm where radar and communication systems operate independently but share the same spectral resources, requiring coordination or interference mitigation between them.

- **Joint Communication and Radar (JCAS):**

- A unified framework that enables the simultaneous operation of radar sensing and communication functions using shared spectral, hardware, and time resources.

- **Dual-Functional Radar-Communication (DFRC) System**

- A system architecture that integrates both radar sensing and wireless communication functionalities within a common platform, providing dual-functionalities.
- **Time Division Duplex (TDD) Radar:**
 - A resource allocation strategy for an JCAS system where radar and communication functions are alternated in separate time slots to avoid mutual interference.
- **Communication-Centric Waveform:**
 - A waveform primarily designed for communication purposes, which is exploited for radar sensing as well. Single-carrier modulation, orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), orthogonal time frequency space (OTFS), affine frequency division multiplexing (AFDM), etc.
- **Radar-Centric Waveform:**
 - A waveform primarily designed for radar sensing applications, with communication functionalities added as a secondary feature. Phase modulated continuous wave (PMCW), phase-coded Frequency Modulated Continuous Wave (FMCW), index-modulated FMCW, etc.
- **Index Modulation:**
 - A modulation technique that conveys data information by activating specific indices (e.g., antennas, subcarriers, or time slots).
- **Joint Optimisation:**
 - A JCAS signalling design approach that simultaneously optimises both radar sensing and communication performance metrics under shared system constraints.
- **Joint Precoding**
 - A JCAS precoding approach that designs precoding vectors to serve both radar and communication objectives simultaneously, often leveraging multi-antenna systems.
- **Full-Duplex (FD) JCAS**
 - A JCAS system configuration where radar sensing and DL/UL communication operations are performed simultaneously over the same frequency band using advanced self-interference cancellation techniques.
- **Downlink (DL) JCAS:**
 - A JCAS operation mode where the transmitter (e.g., base station (BS)) performs both communication to the user and radar sensing of targets.
- **Uplink (UL) JCAS:**
 - A JCAS operation mode where the UE or sensor transmits signals that are used both for communication to the BS and for radar sensing purposes.
- **Mono-static JCAS:**
 - A JCAS configuration where the transmitter and receiver for radar sensing are co-located at the same communication node.
- **Bi-static JCAS:**

- A JCAS configuration where the transmitter and receiver are at different communication nodes, enabling spatially separated sensing.
- **Multistatic JCAS:**
 - A JCAS configuration where multiple spatially distributed transmitters and/or receivers collaboratively perform radar sensing tasks.
- **Distributed JCAS (or Network-Level JCAS):**
 - A configuration in which multiple widely distributed nodes collaborate to perform radar sensing and communication tasks for improved spatial coverage and robustness
- **Cooperative JCAS:**
 - A collaborative JCAS approach where nodes actively exchange information and coordinate their operations to enhance the joint performance of sensing and communication.

2.1.4 Synchronisation Related Definitions

2.1.4.1 Single Source

This refers to synchronisation characteristics relative to a single clock source or signal generator. Key terms include:

- **Clock jitter:**
 - Clock jitter refers to short-term variations in the timing of clock signal edges from their ideal positions in time. It affects the temporal stability of a single clock signal and can degrade system performance, especially in high-speed communication and sensing applications. Jitter is the time-domain manifestation of phase noise, which is the frequency-domain representation of random phase fluctuations in a signal. Specifically, jitter can be calculated from phase noise by integrating the single-sideband (SSB) phase noise spectrum over a specified frequency offset range and converting the result into time units.

$$RMS\ Jitter = \frac{1}{2\pi f_{carrier}} \sqrt{2 \int_{f_2}^{f_1} L(f) df}$$

where $L(f)$ is the phase noise in linear units (i.e. not dBc/Hz), and $f_{carrier}$ is the carrier frequency.

- **Phase noise:**
 - Phase noise is the frequency-domain representation of the short-term random fluctuations in the phase of a signal, typically originating from thermal noise, flicker noise, power supply variations, or active device instabilities in oscillators and clocks. It describes how the energy of a signal, ideally concentrated at a single frequency (the carrier), spreads into nearby frequencies due to these phase instabilities. Phase noise is usually expressed in dBc/Hz (decibels relative to the carrier, per hertz of bandwidth), and plotted as a function of frequency offset from the carrier frequency. A typical phase noise plot shows the degradation in signal purity at increasing frequency offsets (e.g., 1 Hz, 10 Hz, 1 kHz, etc.).

2.1.4.2 Multiple Sources

This addresses synchronisation between two or more independent clocks or systems. Key terms include:

- **Time offset:**
 - Time offset is the absolute difference in time between two clocks at a given instant. It represents a static or dynamic discrepancy in their time bases. Time offset is critical in applications like timestamping, time-of-arrival (ToA) measurements, and coordinated transmissions. Example: If Clock A reads 10.000000 ms and Clock B reads 10.000020 ms, the time offset is 20 ns.
- **Frequency offset:**
 - Frequency offset is the difference in the clock rates (i.e., the number of ticks per second) between two systems. Even minor mismatches in frequency can cause increasing divergence in time offset over long durations if not corrected. Example: A 1 ppm frequency offset causes a 1 μ s drift every second.
- **Phase offset:**
 - Phase offset refers to the difference in phase angle between two periodic signals, even if their frequencies are identical. It is typically measured in degrees or radians and is particularly important in systems relying on coherent processing, beamforming, or MIMO. Example: Two clocks may tick at exactly 1 MHz, but one may lag the other by 90° (or a quarter of a cycle).
- **Relative jitter:**
 - Relative jitter describes the variation in timing difference between two synchronized clocks over time. It arises due to noise, temperature variation, interference, or imperfections in synchronisation mechanisms. It reflects how consistently the synchronisation between the two systems is maintained.

Note: This is distinct from absolute jitter (which measures a single clock's variation); relative jitter is critical in applications requiring stable inter-device timing, such as distributed (cell-free) MIMO, phased arrays, or collaborative sensing.

2.2 Synchronisation

Synchronisation refers to the process of aligning parameters, such as time, frequency, and phase, across distributed systems. In 6G and beyond, especially within JCAS systems, precise synchronisation is essential for enabling coherent processing, accurate localisation, and reliable data fusion.

As JCAS integrates sensing and communication functions across tightly coordinated nodes, maintaining a standard time and frequency reference becomes a critical requirement. This section defines the key synchronisation concepts: time synchronisation, clock frequency synchronisation, and clock phase synchronisation.

2.2.1 Time-Synchronisation

Time synchronisation is the process of calibrating the time of a subordinate clock to match that of a master clock, ensuring that both operate on a standard temporal reference. This involves compensating for transmission delays and clock offsets, often through repeated exchanges of timing

information. While perfect alignment is not achievable due to inherent system delays and noise, synchronisation aims to minimize the time error between clocks to within an acceptable margin.

In JCAS systems, accurate time synchronisation is critical to enable coherent signal processing, reliable data fusion, and precise localisation, all of which depend on a shared and highly accurate time base across distributed nodes.

2.2.2 Frequency-Synchronisation

Clock frequency synchronisation is the process of aligning the rate of ticking, that is, the clock frequency f of a subordinate clock with that of a master clock. It is achieved when both clocks operate at the same nominal frequency, ensuring that the time interval between successive clock pulses is consistent across the clocks. Although their absolute time values may still differ, frequency synchronisation ensures that both clocks tick at the same rate. This consistency is essential for maintaining long-term alignment and preventing time drift between distributed systems.

2.2.3 Phase-synchronisation

Clock phase synchronisation refers to the alignment of the clock phase ϕ , ensuring that the subordinate clock ticks at the same instant as the master clock. This involves adjusting the time origin of the subordinate clock so that its ticks occur simultaneously with those of the master. Phase synchronisation inherently requires frequency synchronisation and represents a more stringent form of alignment. Clock frequency and phase synchronisation are closely related, as the clock frequency is the derivative of the clock phase with respect to time:

$$f(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{d\phi}{dt}$$

Thus, achieving phase synchronisation implies very precise frequency synchronisation. In practice, frequency synchronisation is typically performed first, followed by finer adjustments to achieve phase synchronisation.

3 Synchronisation Requirements and Challenges

Accurate synchronisation is fundamental for the operation of wireless communication and radar systems. In wireless communication networks, it ensures orthogonal transmission, accurate channel estimation, and proper alignment of time and frequency resources [1]. In TDD operation, precise synchronisation avoids intra-cell and inter-cell interference. In radar systems, synchronisation is essential for achieving accurate delay estimation and coherent signal processing [2]. As these technologies converge under the JCAS paradigm, understanding the baseline synchronisation performance of current systems is important to identify the limitations and trade-offs that must be addressed to enable joint operation.

3.1 Overview of Synchronisation Requirements

This section first reviews the performance goals that 6G-MUSICAL aims to meet and the levels of accuracy required for reliable operation. First, it briefly reviews the performance requirements of 5G-New Radio (NR) and then presents the envisioned performance goals of 6G-MUSICAL. Then, the key technical challenges that limit the ability to maintain high-precision synchronisation across diverse nodes and environments are examined.

3.1.1 Performance Goals

Synchronisation requirements vary depending on the application. For example, in cellular communication, BSs are typically synchronized within microseconds, depending on the access technique and deployment scenario. This level of synchronisation is enough to support frame alignment and avoid ISI. In contrast, sensing systems often require much tighter synchronisation. For instance, achieving meter-level positioning accuracy demands accurate delay estimates, within a few nanoseconds, since a 1 ns timing error translates into a 30 cm range [3].

As already mentioned, the consequences of synchronisation errors differ across systems. In sensing, time alignment error (TAE) leads to biased range estimates in TOA and time-difference-of-arrival (TDOA) methods. Even nanosecond-level timing errors can result in meter-scale range deviations, severely degrading localisation and tracking [4]. Carrier frequency offset (CFO), often caused by oscillator mismatches, introduces ambiguity in Doppler estimation and affects velocity tracking. In addition, phase offset limits the ability to perform coherent signal processing across distributed nodes. In wireless communication systems, some synchronisation-related impairments can be tolerated or compensated through signal processing [3]. For example, small propagation delays and timing offsets are typically compensated during symbol timing recovery and channel estimation.

However, in JCAS systems, the receiver usually simultaneously supports multiple objectives. While communication decoding can tolerate and correct some timing offsets, radar-based sensing requires accurate preservation of time to extract parameters such as delay. This creates a fundamental difference in how synchronisation impacts each function. These differences highlight the need for a deeper understanding of current systems' synchronisation capabilities and limitations, especially when moving toward unified JCAS architectures.

3.1.2 Synchronisation within 5G-NR

Synchronisation in 5G NR is essential to ensure both link-level performance and network-level coordination. For link-level, the synchronisation between a BS and UE allows for reliable demodulation, accurate channel estimation, and proper resource alignment. For network-level coordination, the synchronisation between multiple BSs or transmission points is fundamental for achieving cell-phase alignment and supporting coordinated features such as coordinated multipoint

(CoMP) and network-assisted positioning [5].

An elementary synchronisation requirement in 5G-NR networks, especially those operating in TDD mode, is cell phase synchronisation. As specified by 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), 5G NR-TDD systems must maintain a timing alignment within $\pm 1.5 \mu\text{s}$ (i.e., total $3 \mu\text{s}$ cell phase sync window) across all antennas [6]. This ensures that DL and UP transmissions do not interfere with one another in neighbouring cells, and that multiple operators can coexist in shared spectrum and geographic regions. This requirement applies to the antenna reference points and is tied to a common time source, typically traceable to Coordinated Universal Time (UTC). This synchronisation requirement is also known as absolute time error, and it is illustrated in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1: Absolute versus relative time alignment error (TAE) in 5G-NR [5].

For coordinated features such as carrier aggregation (CA), dual connectivity (DC), and CoMP, synchronisation requirements may become more stringent. These features rely on cooperation between multiple BSs to enhance throughput, coverage, or reliability. However, the synchronisation requirements apply only to the nodes participating in the coordination. This means that timing constraints are relative among the antennas within a given coordination area, rather than requiring alignment to a global reference. As illustrated in Figure 3-1, each coordination area has its own relative TAE specification. For example, the figure shows two independent coordination areas, each with different synchronisation requirements, such as 130 ns and 260 ns, respectively [5].

To address this, 3GPP introduced the concept of Maximum Relative Timing Difference (MRTD) [7], which quantifies the maximum allowed difference in signal arrival time at the UE due to BS TAE and RF propagation delay difference ΔT_{prop} , i.e., $MRTD = TAE + \Delta T_{prop}$.

The most stringent BS TAE requirements range from 65 ns to 260 ns, but these apply only in intra-site or collocated deployments, and not for backhaul-based scenarios. This means that high-precision synchronisation is primarily needed within localised coordination zones, while looser timing bounds are acceptable in the network.

3.1.3 6G-MUSICAL Goals in terms of Synchronisation Requirements

To meet the strict synchronisation requirements introduced by multistatic configurations and centimetre-level localisation, the project goes beyond conventional GPS-based and Precision Time Protocol (PTP) timing systems, which fall short in both precision and reliability for high-resolution

sensing applications. More specifically, the current synchronisation technologies used by wireless communication networks are inadequate for enabling 3D imaging.

To overcome these limitations, the project will leverage advanced optical technologies to generate and distribute low-noise, highly stable clock and frequency references to edge nodes. Synchronisation across nodes will be achieved using a hybrid strategy that combines optical fibre-based delivery of reference signals with LoS over-the-air synchronisation mechanisms. The following synchronisation-related performance requirements are set:

- Ultra-low timing jitter (KPI 3.2): The system must achieve absolute jitter below 100 fs and relative jitter below 500 fs between distributed nodes. This level of precision is crucial to maintain phase coherence across multiple antennas or sensing nodes, enabling long coherent processing intervals and precise Doppler estimation.
- Minimal clock timing error (KPI 3.3): Absolute clock synchronisation error must be maintained below 50 ps. This ensures sufficient timing accuracy for TOA and TDOA-based positioning techniques, enabling localisation accuracy at the centimetre level. It also supports precise frame alignment and synchronisation across dense deployments.
- High-accuracy reference source (KPI 3.4): The system must be based on a reference source with a frequency stability of at least 10^{-13} at 1 second. Such high stability reduces the need for frequent recalibration, ensures long-term coherence, and supports both sensing and communication at high carrier frequencies with minimal drift.
- Low inter-node timing deviation (KPI 3.5): The maximum allowable timing deviation between any two nodes must be less than 30 ps. Tight inter-node synchronisation is essential for forming virtual arrays in distributed radar systems, enabling accurate beamforming, spatial diversity exploitation, and coherent data fusion across the network.

3.1.4 Challenges in Achieving High-Precision Synchronisation

Current mobile backhaul and front-haul networks cannot provide scalable and low-cost time synchronisation with sub-nanosecond accuracy, which is at the core of 6G and timing-critical applications. Low-cost time synchronization protocols, such as the PTP, only achieve microsecond accuracies due to the frequency deviation between device clocks [8]. A possible solution would be to implement rubidium atomic clocks but equipping each user with such a high-cost, high-power-consumption device would be impractical.

A more viable solution is user device clock synchronisation. This typically requires low-jitter clock frequency synchronisation in conjunction with a clock-phase-tracking method. Key example approaches include White Rabbit [9] and clock phase caching [10], both of which require a low-jitter frequency-synchronized clock signal, achieved either by recovering the clock frequency from data and performing clock jitter removal (for example, synchronous Ethernet, SyncE) [11] or by transmitting a dedicated clock signal. While SyncE can introduce time errors of up to 20 ns due to phase wander from jitter filtering, dedicated low-jitter clock signals can achieve picosecond-level accuracy, offering significantly better performance. However, despite successful demonstrations of optical clock synchronization in short-range contexts like intra-data-centre networks, a scalable, cost-effective solution for achieving low-jitter frequency synchronization is still lacking.

3.2 Mono-Static Vs Bistatic Sensing Synchronisation Requirements

As the ultimate goal of 6GMUSICAL is to contribute to enabling radar-based functionalities within wireless communication networks, analysing the synchronisation requirements of different radar

topologies becomes essential. In this context, we begin with the monostatic radar configuration, where the transmitter and receiver are co-located. This topology simplifies synchronisation requirements, as transmitter and receiver circuitry share a common local oscillator. Consequently, synchronisation with external sources is not required, and system performance primarily depends on the stability of the local oscillator. However, maintaining internal phase stability is still important, particularly over long coherent processing intervals where oscillator drift or phase noise can impact performance [3]. Nonetheless, if coordination with other nodes is needed for data fusion or joint sensing, some level of network-wide timing alignment may be required. Additionally, implementing full-duplex operation establishes practical challenges such as self-interference suppression. To avoid the hardware complexity and self-interference associated with full-duplex operation, alternative configurations such as bistatic and multistatic are strong candidates for enabling a sensing component in wireless networks [4].

Unlike monostatic radar, bistatic radar systems involve a transmitter and receiver that are located at different geographic positions, as illustrated in Figure 3-2. This separation introduces synchronisation challenges that must be carefully addressed [3] [4]. The most critical among them is timing offset (TO), which directly affects the accuracy of bistatic delay measurements and thus target localisation. In addition, CFO, arising from independent oscillators at each node, can impair Doppler estimation and phase stability. Other relevant issues include sampling frequency offset (SFO) and clock drift, which can accumulate over time and degrade signal alignment.

For example, accurately estimating the target delay requires tight time synchronisation between the transmitter and receiver. Even small timing offsets can bias the measured delay, resulting in errors in bistatic range estimation and, ultimately, in the inferred target position.

Figure 3-2: Time offset in bi-static radar topologies.

As shown in Figure 3-2 the bistatic delay measurement defines an ellipse, with the transmitter and receiver as its foci. In the ideal case, the actual target location lies on this ellipse. However, when there is a synchronisation error, such as a timing mismatch ΔT between the transmitter and receiver, the measured delay is biased, which shifts the corresponding ellipse. This displacement misaligns the region used for localisation, resulting in a systematic bias in the estimated target position. The figure illustrates this by comparing the nominal ellipse to a displaced version caused by a small TO, showing the resulting shift in the apparent target location.

To ensure accurate localisation, synchronisation must be significantly finer than the resolution implied by the desired spatial accuracy. For example, achieving a 1-meter range accuracy requires timing

errors below approximately 3.3 nanoseconds, or even picosecond, synchronisation precision across bistatic pairs. If synchronisation errors increase, they propagate directly into the estimated target position, degrading the overall sensing performance.

This challenge becomes even more critical in multistatic configurations, where multiple receivers simultaneously measure bistatic delays relative to a standard transmitter. In this case, each TOA measurement defines a distinct ellipse, and the target is estimated at the intersection of these ellipses. However, residual timing errors between the transmitter and each receiver can shift the corresponding ellipses inconsistently, distorting the intersection region and degrading localisation accuracy.

Furthermore, phase synchronisation becomes essential when the system performs coherent processing across receivers. In such cases, the received signals from different spatially distributed nodes are combined coherently to enhance detection performance or improve localisation precision through phase-based techniques. Any phase offset, arising from unsynchronised local oscillators or channel-dependent phase drifts, can cause destructive interference or misalignment in the combined signal, leading to errors in estimating the target's position. Consequently, maintaining stable and consistent phase references across nodes is critical to preserving the spatial resolution and accuracy of multistatic coherent sensing systems [12].

4 Selection of Transmitter-Receivers for Multistatic Sensing

4.1 Context and Motivation

Enabling sensing functionalities within wireless communication networks has raised significant interest in recent years [13]. This evolution is driven by the emergence of new use cases, demanding radar-based capabilities such as environmental awareness, localisation, and tracking capabilities. These capabilities are essential for applications such as autonomous mobility and smart infrastructure. By sharing spectrum, hardware, and infrastructure, JCAS-enabled networks allow more efficient use of resources while unlocking new use cases [14].

In line with the vision of JCAS-enabled networks, Figure 4-1 depicts an architecture that integrates a sensing component into next-generation networks. This general architecture was proposed in [4]; however, it is envisioned that the upcoming transmitter and receiver selection algorithm will build upon this scenario. Thus, the following revisits the general architecture introduced in [4].

Figure 4-1: JCAS-Enabled Networks Architecture.

The Figure 4-1 illustrates a JCAS-enabled network architecture, where a central unit (CU) manages two distinct serving areas (SAs). The radio sensing functionality is supported via a multistatic configuration, leveraging spatial diversity across the SAs to enhance sensing performance. This setup enables joint transmission, reception, and sensing across multiple distributed nodes under the coordination of the CU.

Figure 4-1 illustrates an ultra-dense network (UDN) scenario characterised by a high concentration of BSs, radio units (RUs), and devices that function as communication and/or radio-sensing nodes. The primary distinction between BSs and RUs lies in their coverage, computational power, and antenna capabilities; BSs generally offer wider coverage and greater processing capacity. The dense deployment of nodes enhances spatial diversity, which can be harnessed to improve radio-sensing performance. In particular, targets can be illuminated from multiple angles, exploiting variations in RCS to gain richer sensing information. This spatial diversity, when combined with advanced signal processing techniques such as those enabled by artificial intelligence (AI), supports high-value services like 3D image reconstruction and allows a broad range of applications.

The network architecture follows the cloud radio access network (C-RAN) paradigm, where radio signals are aggregated at a CU for joint processing. To alleviate fronthaul constraints, however, some functional splitting may be implemented. For example, from a sensing perspective, initial estimation or pre-processing tasks could be distributed across the nodes to reduce data transfer requirements.

In the proposed architecture, the radio-sensing component relies on the concept of cooperative multistatic radar, in which a set of network nodes are configured as transmitters while others act as receivers. To organize this cooperation, the network coverage is partitioned into sensing SAs, each defined as a group of nodes that jointly use the same radio resources for sensing purposes.

As illustrated in Figure 4-1, two SAs are considered as an example, where cooperation within and across these areas allows for dynamic allocation of radio resources. The BSs and RUs within SA1 transmit using carrier F1, while those in SA2 receive on the same carrier, thereby forming a multistatic radar. Conversely, if the network elements in SA2 transmit on carrier F2, and those in SA1 receive on F2, a second multistatic radar is established. This approach highlights the need for a dedicated clustering function that dynamically configures the SAs and defines their roles (transmit or receive) based on sensing requirements and node capabilities. This function is responsible for forming multistatic radar instances, coordinating transmissions, and optimising shared resource use.

4.2 Basis for Selection Criteria

As previously mentioned, to make sensing scalable and efficient in dense wireless networks, the system should not consider all nodes as equally involved in every sensing task. Instead, a fundamental aspect is the configuration of transmit and receive roles among the nodes [15]. These clusters define which nodes will cooperate to perform a specific sensing-related task and how the roles of transmitters and receivers are assigned within each cluster. The clustering approach allows the system to optimally allocate resources, namely focusing sensing resources on where they are most needed. For example, APs near a moving target or a surveillance zone can be grouped to form a multistatic radar optimised for observing that specific region.

Therefore, the assignment of these roles should follow a target-centric approach [16], where the selection may depend on several aspects such as distance to the specific regions of interest to be scanned, and performance requirements. For instance, although there may be nodes near the target area, their involvement may not be necessary or effective if they do not have the required capabilities, such as bandwidth, transmit power and computational capacity, to meet the performance requirements. Other selection factors may include the orientation and antenna configuration of the nodes, their current load and availability of radio and computational resources, LoS conditions, their synchronisation accuracy for cooperative sensing, and their compatibility with the waveform or protocol to be used. The target-centric clustering approach presents parallels with user-centric designs in communication systems [17] but shifts the focus from UE to sensing objectives. In this paradigm, the clustering is not static, but it can be adapted in real time based on the mobility of the target, environmental conditions, or sensing performance feedback.

In the proposed framework [4], this is achieved by forming multistatic radar pairs between sensing SAs. For example, assigning the nodes in SA1 as transmitters and those in SA2 as receivers establishes a multistatic radar setup, where probing signals from SA1 are reflected by the environment and captured by SA2. Therefore, the focus here is on the selection criteria for the transmitters and receivers in multistatic sensing. Building upon this, we first describe the architecture of the sensing clustering interface manager (SCIM), which is the function responsible for creating the SAs. Then, initial efforts toward methods for the selection criteria are introduced.

4.2.1 SCIM Functional Architecture

As pointed out, the formation of transmitter-receiver (Tx-Rx) pairs for multistatic sensing in a JCAS-enabled network involves a wide range of factors, including user-defined sensing objectives, network resource constraints, and infrastructure capabilities. To manage this complexity, a structured

architecture is required that enables intelligent decision-making and dynamic reconfiguration. Figure 4-2 **Error! Reference source not found.** illustrates the functional architecture of the sensing clustering manager function, highlighting how sensing missions are translated into technical parameters, how system resources and topology are taken into account, and how the resulting configurations are communicated to the network. At the core of the architecture lies the SCIM, which interacts with several modules and databases to support real-time and context-aware selection of Tx-Rx pairs that satisfy the performance and operational constraints of the network.

Figure 4-2: Functional Architecture of the Sensing Clustering Function.

The SCIM is the responsible for configuring infrastructure nodes to enable efficient and accurate multistatic sensing. This manager orchestrates the selection of nodes to act as transmitters and receivers for each sensing mission. Based on both user-defined requirements and the current network state, it intelligently forms Tx-Rx pairs to optimise bistatic geometry, spatial coverage, and overall sensing performance. In addition to nodes configuration, it allocates the necessary radio and computational resources, such as frequency bands, time slots, transmit power, and processing capacity, so that performance targets related to resolution, accuracy, imaging capability, and tracking requirements are met. This process is carried out in a way that allows sensing operations to coexist harmoniously with ongoing communication services.

To support these decisions, SCIM interacts with several databases and modules. For example, the SCIM relies on a Resource Availability Database (RAD), which provides real-time information on system resources. This includes data such as available spectrum in time and frequency, available transmission power, processing load per AP, and overall network utilization. The database operates in both directions: it supplies SCIM with the current state of the system and is updated accordingly once specific resources are allocated to a sensing mission. This dynamic feedback loop enables continuous monitoring and adjustment of resource allocation, ensuring efficient and conflict-free system operation. Note that the RAD may also be updated by other managers, such as communication-related interfaces in JCAS-enabled networks.

Complementing this is the Network Configuration Database (NCD), which contains static or semi-static information about the deployment environment. Updated less frequently, typically by network operators, this profile stores essential contextual data such as the geographical positions of nodes, their antenna configurations, fronthaul and backhaul capabilities, and environmental parameters like clutter level. The latter may be previously obtained through site surveys or simulations and play an essential role in evaluating sensing feasibility and designing effective cluster formations, particularly in scenarios where propagation conditions are complex or infrastructure varies in capability.

The architecture also includes an Application Interface Module (AIM), which manages interactions between users and the network. It interprets high-level mission requests like surveillance, imaging, or target tracking, and translates them into technical requirements. These include desired range, velocity

and spatial resolutions, accuracy, coverage area, and whether advanced capabilities like imaging or continuous tracking are needed. This interface guarantees that the user's purpose is captured effectively and transformed into sensing parameters.

In parallel, the Communication Interface Module (CIM) ensures close coordination with the network's communication functions, which is critical in JCAS environments where sensing and communication coexist over shared infrastructure. This module provides SCIM with updated scheduling information, awareness of communication traffic levels per node, and insight into whether existing communication waveforms like UL signals from user equipment can be exploited for passive sensing. In both CoMP and cell-free (CF) communication paradigms, this coordination ensures that sensing operations are deployed without compromising communication performance and that opportunities for joint optimisation are fully exploited. The following explores method for the selection of transmitter-receiver pairs.

4.2.1.1 Two-Stage Transmitter–Receiver Selection via Distributed MIMO Radar Systems

The system considered consists of a distributed MIMO radar architecture comprising M transmitter antennas and N receiver antennas deployed over a geographical area of interest. Each antenna node is connected to a central processing unit (CPU), which coordinates signal transmission, reception, and processing tasks. The transmitter nodes are denoted as $T_m = [x_{tm}, y_{tm}]$ for $m = 1, \dots, M$, while the receiver nodes are denoted as $R_n = [x_{rn}, y_{rn}]$ for $n = 1, \dots, N$. These nodes are spatially distributed to ensure coverage diversity and enable multistatic sensing capabilities.

The objective is to detect and localize multiple targets, whose unknown positions are represented by $X_q = [x_q, y_q]$ for $q = 1, \dots, Q$. Each node can operate with a single antenna element, transmitting or receiving signals depending on its assigned role. The scenario is illustrated in Figure 4-3 where the green and blue squares represent the positions of transmitter and receiver antennas, respectively. Red circles indicate targets to be detected. All signals are forwarded to and from the CPU for centralized processing and coordination. Notice that in Figure 4-3, the locations of transmitters and receivers are indicative, but they can be allocated to any place.

Figure 4-3: Distributed MIMO radar with M transmitting, and N receiving antennas, and Q point-like targets.

The proposed method for node selection in distributed MIMO radar is based on a two-stage process that leverages initial low-complexity measurements, followed by a second stage to improve sensing performance. In the first stage, each transmitter antenna transmits an orthogonal waveform that allows the receivers to distinguish between different transmitted signals. As signals propagate through

the environment and reflect off potential targets, the receivers collect these echoes and compute the radar image for each transmitter-receiver pair. This processing enables the estimation of signal returns at different positions within the area of interest, which is discretized into spatial bins identified by coordinates (x, y) .

For each bin location (x, y) , a SNR map is constructed across all possible transmitter-receiver combinations. This map reveals how well each pair perceives the target's presence at that specific position, offering a qualitative indication of detection likelihood. Table 1 illustrates this SNR mapping, where the rows represent transmitters and the columns represent receivers. Each entry in the table is labelled as H (high), M (medium), or L (low), representing the received signal quality for a specific pair.

Based on the generated SNR map, transmitter-receiver pairs that report high or medium values for a given pixel are selected as candidates for sensing that position. These pairs are then grouped into sensing areas (SAs) tailored to the potential target locations. In the second stage of the method, more sophisticated beamforming techniques are applied using the selected pairs. This focused processing enhances detection, parameter estimation, and tracking accuracy by concentrating the spatial gain on the region of interest.

Table 1: SNR mapping for transmitter–receiver pairs at position (x, y)

	Receiver 1	Receiver 2	Receiver 3	Receiver N
Transmitter 1	H	M	M	L
Transmitter 2	M	H	H	M
Transmitter 3	L	H	H	H
Transmitter M	M	L	H	M

While the SNR map is the primary criterion for selecting the participating APs, other factors must also be considered. These include the sensing requirements of the application, such as resolution and coverage constraints, as well as the individual capabilities of each node, including bandwidth availability, computational resources, and beam steering flexibility. The final selection process thus balances detection performance with system-level constraints to enable adaptive, efficient, and high-quality radar sensing. The sensing requirements and node capabilities are described in detail in Subsections 4.2.1 and 4.2.3, respectively.

4.2.2 Sensing Requirements

As previously discussed, the methodology for determining which transmitter–receiver pairs are involved in sensing is controlled not only by signal quality metrics, such as the SNR mapping described earlier, but also by the sensing requirements. These requirements may vary according to the intended sensing task (e.g., target detection, tracking, or imaging), and the environmental conditions. The following describes several key considerations that the SCIM must consider from the perspective of

sensing requirements.

- **Resolution:** When high resolution is required, for example, in imaging or precise localisation tasks, this typically implies the need for greater system resources, such as increased bandwidth or favourable node geometry. The SCIM should consider these needs by selecting nodes that can support the resolution demand, whether through available bandwidth, appropriate spatial distribution, or both.
- **Target type and size:** The nature of the target, whether it is a point target or an extended object, influences the suitable sensing configuration. For extended targets, multistatic observations (i.e., using different Tx–Rx positions) provide richer information through multiple viewing angles. Conversely, point targets may be effectively detected using monostatic or bistatic configurations. The SCIM should adapt the cluster formation accordingly.
- **Temporal constraints:** Sensing applications may have different latency and update rate requirements. For real-time applications such as autonomous driving or gesture recognition, the sensing cluster must support rapid data acquisition and processing. This may constrain how frequently node configurations can change and require the SCIM to maintain cluster stability. In contrast, for applications with relaxed timing constraints, clusters can be more flexibly adapted over time to optimise performance.
- **Coverage vs. accuracy:** The SCIM may need to balance between covering a large area with moderate precision and focusing sensing resources on a small region with high accuracy. Wide-area coverage is typically achieved by involving more dispersed nodes, while accurate localisation may require closer, better-aligned Tx–Rx pairs. The decision depends on the sensing goals and should be dynamically handled by the SCIM.
- **Redundancy:** In safety-critical scenarios, robustness takes priority over efficiency. The SCIM may deliberately introduce redundancy into the sensing clusters, selecting overlapping or partially redundant Tx–Rx pairs to ensure continued operation in the presence of node failures or channel degradation. This is particularly important in automotive, industrial, or defence applications.
- **Spatial diversity:** Selecting nodes with different positions not only enhances resolution but also improves robustness against fading, blockage, or environmental uncertainties. The SCIM should consider not just distance or angle but also ensure spatial diversity in the selected cluster to maximize sensing reliability.

4.2.3 Node Capabilities

In addition to meeting sensing performance requirements, the selection of nodes must also consider the capabilities and limitations of the individual transmitter and receiver nodes. Since the system relies on heterogeneous infrastructure (i.e., BSs, and RUs) the SCIM should consider the different nodes' capabilities to create sensing clusters that are both feasible and efficient. Selecting nodes without regard to their resource availability or hardware constraints can result in suboptimal sensing performance, increased latency, or even task failure. Below, we describe several important criteria that must be evaluated by the SCIM when selecting nodes from the perspective of their capabilities.

- **Relative position to the location of interest:** Although the primary selection may be driven by the desired sensing direction or coverage, not all nearby nodes are equally suitable. The SCIM must consider the geometric configuration of each node with respect to the sensing region. This includes LoS availability, expected signal strength, and angular diversity. Nodes poorly positioned relative to the region may be excluded despite their other capabilities. For

example, spatial resolution is poor for the area near the line connecting the Tx/Rx pair [18]. Figure 4-4 highlights spatial resolution variations for a bistatic Tx/Rx pair in a 2D scenario which remains valid for the 3D scenario as well.

Figure 4-4: Spatial resolution in bistatic sensing.

Red coloured elliptical paths correspond to different range bins in the range-Doppler (RD) map and blue line are AoAs. We define the spatial resolution as the distance between the consecutive elliptical paths along a particular AoA direction. Regions closer to the line joining Tx and Rx are low in the spatial resolution. It is important to note that with a bistatic sensing, maximum spatial resolution is the upper bounded by monostatic range resolution (bandwidth dependent). This provides a base to define a criterion for the selection of bistatic pairs when targeting a particular region for sensing. Figure 4-5 shows a multistatic sensing scenario where a target is detected by four receiver nodes, coloured dotted lines indicate spatial grid along the AoAs. It can be seen that Rx_3 and Rx_4 show better spatial resolution compared to Rx_1 and Rx_2 due to the bistatic geometry with the Tx.

Figure 4-5: Multistatic sensing scenario highlighting suitability of Tx/Rx pairs for a target in the coverage area.

- Bandwidth availability: In JCAS systems, nodes often serve dual roles. If an AP is currently

occupied with high-throughput communication tasks, it may have reduced bandwidth available for sensing. The SCIM must monitor the current load on each node and prioritize those with sufficient bandwidth to support the desired radar waveform characteristics, such as pulse duration, repetition frequency, or resolution.

- **Synchronisation accuracy:** Accurate synchronisation across distributed nodes is essential for coherent processing in bistatic and multistatic radar configurations. Nodes with lower synchronisation precision may introduce phase errors or timing jitter, degrading the radar performance. The SCIM should assess synchronisation accuracy and select nodes with high timing accuracy when coherent detection or high-resolution estimation is required.
- **Antenna configuration:** The sensing potential of a node is also related to its configuration. Nodes equipped with multiple antenna elements can enable advanced features such as MIMO processing, spatial filtering, and beamforming. The SCIM should leverage this heterogeneity by assigning more demanding or flexible sensing tasks to nodes with enhanced antenna architectures, thereby maximizing the effectiveness of the sensing cluster.
- **Processing and energy constraints:** The network may include nodes with limited computational or energy budgets. High-complexity signal processing tasks should be avoided on constrained nodes. Instead, the SCIM may delegate such tasks to more powerful nodes or reserve the constrained nodes for simpler operations like signal forwarding or initial detection.
- **Fronthaul capacity:** Centralized processing in a cloud-RAN-like architecture often requires nodes to transmit raw or partially processed data to a CPU. Nodes with limited fronthaul capacity, intermittent connectivity, or long delays are not suitable for applications that require high-volume data transmission. The SCIM must consider communication link quality when assigning roles that rely on real-time cooperation or centralized fusion.

5 Cooperative Sensing Algorithms

Cooperative sensing refers to the use of multiple distributed sensing units that work together to observe a shared environment and jointly estimate parameters of interest, such as target locations. This cooperation enhances spatial diversity, improves robust detection, and reduces ambiguity compared to isolated processing. In the context of distributed MIMO radar, cooperative algorithms allow multiple transmitters (Tx) and receivers (Rx) to work together by combining their observations to estimate the target location more accurately. Therefore, this section presents a cooperative sensing algorithm in which each receiver node independently estimates propagation delays based on an interleaved OFDM waveform. These local estimates are then collected at a CPU that performs signal fusion and target localisation. The proposed method supports three signal processing modes: non-coherent, coherent, and hybrid processing, which allows the system to adapt to different synchronisation and deployment scenarios.

This section begins by presenting the system model, followed by the cooperative signal processing algorithm and its three processing modes. It concludes with numerical results that evaluate the performance of each scenario under different deployment and processing configurations.

5.1 System Model

This work considers a distributed MIMO radar system, as illustrated in Figure 4-3, designed for environment sensing using an interleaved OFDM waveform to enable sensing functionalities by exploiting spatial diversity across distributed antenna elements.

The radar system architecture consists of M transmitting antennas located at coordinates $T_m = [x_{tm}; y_{tm}]$ for $m = 1, \dots, M$, and N receiving antennas positioned at $R_n = [x_{rn}; y_{rn}]$ for $n = 1, \dots, N$. The signals from these antennas are transported through a fiber-based fronthaul to the CPU, where either full or partial signal processing is performed. This architecture facilitates coherent, non-coherent, or hybrid (coherent and non-coherent) signal integration across multiple spatially separated units, enhancing the radar system's performance in terms of target detection and parameter estimation.

5.1.1 Transmitted Signal

The time-domain OFDM signal transmitted by the m th AP is given by

$$x_m = F^H b_m, \quad (1)$$

where $b_m \in \mathbb{C}^K$ represents the interleaved OFDM data vector for transmitter m , and $F \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times K}$ is the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) matrix, where K denotes the number of subcarriers. In the adopted interleaved OFDM scheme, each AP is allocated a distinct subset of non-overlapping subcarriers. This ensures that each AP transmits a unique subset of subcarriers. Therefore, the signals satisfy the orthogonality condition, i.e., $x_i^H x_m = 0$, $i \neq m$ which guarantees mutual orthogonality among the transmitted waveforms.

5.1.2 Received Signal

The signals transmitted by the M distributed antennas are reflected by Q targets. After applying the DFT at the n th receiver, the resulting frequency-domain signal is expressed as

$$r_n = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{q=1}^Q \gamma_{m,n,q} D_{m,n,q} b_m + n_n, \quad (2)$$

where $\gamma_{m,n,q}$ denotes the RCS of target q as observed by the (m, n) Tx-Rx pair.

Figure 5-1: Schematic illustration of the proposed distributed algorithm for target localisation.

The diagonal matrix $D_{m,n,q} = \text{diag}\{a_{m,n,q}\} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times K}$ represents the frequency-domain channel response for the path (m, n, q) , and $n_n \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_n^2 I)$ represents the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) at the n th receiver, with zero mean and variance σ_n^2 . The k th element of the frequency-domain channel vector $a_{m,n,q}$ is given by

$$a_{m,n,q}(k) = \exp(-j2\pi\Delta f \tau_{m,n,q} k), \quad (3)$$

where Δf denotes the subcarrier spacing, and $\tau_{m,n,q}$ represents the total path delay experienced by the signal traveling from transmitter m to target q , and from target q to

receiver n , i.e., $\tau_{m,n,q} = \tau_{m,q} + \tau_{q,n}$. Herein, $\tau_{m,q}$ and $\tau_{q,n}$ correspond to the propagation delays from the m th transmitter to the q th target, and from the q th target to the n th receiver, respectively.

5.2 Distributed Algorithm

This section introduces a distributed algorithm for target localisation in a MIMO-OFDM radar setting. The algorithm operates in two stages. 1) local delay estimation at each distributed receiver node, and 2) signal fusion at the CPU to estimate target positions. Specifically, each of the distributed N receiver APs independently estimates the Q delays for each Tx-Rx pair. These estimated delays are then offloaded to the CPU, where data fusion is performed for joint target localisation. The distributed algorithm is illustrated in Figure 5-1.

5.2.1 Signal Processing at the n -th Receiver

At the n th receiver, the aggregated data vector, $\mathbf{b} = \sum_{m=1}^M \mathbf{b}_m$, is first removed from the received signal using element-wise division, as discussed in [19]. The resulting signal after data removal can be given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{r}}_n = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{q=1}^Q \gamma_{m,n,q} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{m,n,q} + \mathbf{w}_n, \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_{m,n,q}$ denotes the interleaved version of the frequency-domain channel vector corresponding to the (m, n, q) link, obtained from $\mathbf{D}_{m,n,q} \mathbf{b}_m$. According to (4), to estimate the time delay $\tau_{m,n,q}$ for each target q , an inverse discrete Fourier transform (IDFT) is applied to the vector $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_{m,n,q}$, focusing on the subcarriers assigned to transmitter m .

5.2.2 Signal Processing at the CPU

The estimated delays $\hat{\tau}_{m,n,q}$, previously extracted at each receiver, are forwarded to the CPU, where they are used to reconstruct signal components and compute the final target localisation map. Three processing modes are considered: non-coherent, coherent, and hybrid processing, described in the following subsections.

A. Non-Coherent Processing Mode

In the non-coherent case, the fusion is based on the assumption that the reflectivity coefficients across Tx–Rx pairs are independent, as typically observed when antennas are widely separated and fall outside each other's main lobes [20]. In such processing mode, phase synchronisation among transmitting and receiving antennas is not available. As such, the CPU reconstructs a synthetic signal for each path using delay-based phase shifts. Specifically, let the frequency-domain reconstructed signal for the (m, n) Tx-Rx pair be denoted as $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{m,n}$ and mathematically obtained as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{m,n} = \sum_{q=1}^Q \exp(-j2\pi\Delta f \hat{\tau}_{m,n,q} \mathbf{k}_m), \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{k}_m contains the set of subcarrier indices assigned to the m th transmitter. Target localisation is then achieved by applying a non-coherent matched filter (MF) between the reconstructed signals $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{m,n}$ and the hypothesized response vectors $\mathbf{h}_{m,n}(x, y)$ for each possible target position. The radar imaging function is computed as

$$P^{(nc)}(x, y) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M |\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{m,n}^H \mathbf{h}_{m,n}(x, y)|^2, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_{m,n}(x, y)$ represents the codebook entry corresponding to the (x, y) position. This structure avoids phase coupling, making it robust to synchronisation errors, but at the cost of lower spatial resolution.

B. Coherent Processing Mode

Under coherent processing, the reflectivity coefficients are assumed to be identical across Tx–Rx pairs, justified by the fact that all antennas fall within the same beamwidth and share a common phase reference [20]. This allows coherent summation and improved resolution, as demonstrated in [21]. Therefore, in the coherent processing case, ideal phase synchronisation is assumed across all antennas. The CPU uses the full complex signal model, retaining both magnitude and phase. The reconstructed signal remains as (5), and the fusion uses coherent matched filtering, where all paths are phase-aligned as

$$P^{(c)}(x, y) = \left| \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{m,n}^H \mathbf{h}_{m,n}(x, y) \right|^2. \quad (7)$$

This results in higher resolution and better sidelobe suppression but requires tight synchronisation between all nodes.

C. Hybrid Processing Mode

Hybrid processing leverages terminal-level synchronisation, assuming that antennas are grouped into terminals, where synchronisation is guaranteed within each terminal but not across terminals. This reflects a practical deployment scenario where local phase coherence is feasible, but global coherence is not, i.e., coherent processing is performed within terminals and non-coherent across terminals. Let \mathcal{T}_t denote the antenna pairs within terminal t , and let T be the number of terminals. Within each terminal, coherent processing is applied as

$$P_t(x, y) = \left| \sum_{(m,n) \in \mathcal{T}_t} \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{m,n}^H \mathbf{h}_{m,n}(x, y) \right|^2. \quad (8)$$

Then, non-coherent summation is used across terminals as

$$P^{(hyb)}(x, y) = \sum_{t=1}^T P_t(x, y). \quad (9)$$

This mode provides a trade-off between performance and implementation cost, offering better resolution than non-coherent processing without requiring full network-wide synchronisation.

5.3 Numerical Results

This section evaluates the performance of the proposed distributed localisation algorithm under three distinct system configurations, as summarized in Table 2. Each scenario corresponds to a different processing mode: non-coherent, coherent, and hybrid. The scenarios vary in both the number of transmitting and receiving nodes, as well as the number of antennas per node. The results presented below were obtained using an interleaved OFDM-based system with a bandwidth of 800 MHz, a 28 GHz carrier frequency, and an SNR of 20 dB.

Table 2: Simulation Parameters for joint processing

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
No. Tx/Rx	Multiple	1	Multiple
No. antennas per Tx/Rx	1	Multiple	Multiple
Processing Mode	Non-coherent	Coherent	Hybrid

A. Scenario 1

This scenario considers a distributed MIMO radar system with four widely separated transmitters and four receivers, each equipped with a single antenna, considering a non-coherent signal processing at the CPU (no phase synchronisation). For the radio-sensing channel, three targets are located at coordinates $[-1, -2]$, $[0, 0]$, and $[3, 3]$ meters. The following presents an experimental investigation into the influence of antenna deployment geometry on radar imaging performance. We compared two distinct antenna arrangements: a regularly deployed grid pattern and a randomly distributed configuration. The study employed Monte Carlo simulations with 500 realizations to assess localisation accuracy, quantified via RMSE.

Figure 5-2 shows the radar image obtained using an interleaved OFDM signal with 256 subcarriers. The transmitter antennas were uniformly deployed along the x-axis from 0 to 5 meters, with the y-coordinate fixed at 5 meters. Conversely, the receiver antennas were placed along the y-axis from 0 to 5 meters, with the x-coordinate fixed at 5 meters. From this figure, each Tx-Rx pair operates independently, and the fusion at the CPU is performed non-coherently. Herein, we can observe how the sidelobes are formed by the intersection of the ellipses generated by each Tx-Rx pair. These sidelobes tend to concentrate in specific regions, leaving other areas relatively free of interference. Additionally, the resolution and the overall sidelobe structure are shaped by the regular deployment of the antennas.

Figure 5-2: Radar imaging for scenario 1 in which antennas are regularly deployed along the x- and y-axes.

Similar to Figure 5-2, Figure 5-3 illustrates the radar image obtained using an interleaved OFDM signal with 256 subcarriers. However, in this case, the transmitter and receiver antennas are randomly deployed across the entire area.

Figure 5-3: Radar imaging for a scenario in which antennas are randomly deployed within an area of 100 square meter.

Specifically, each (x, y) coordinate is drawn from a uniform distribution over the range $[-5, 5]$ meters. This figure shows that, compared to the radar imaging in Figure 5-2, the random deployment results in more pronounced sidelobe levels. Specifically, in this case, the sidelobes are spread across the entire area. This spread is due to the diversity in the antenna positions, unlike the regular deployment, where the antennas follow a well-defined pattern. Additionally, it can be observed that, for some targets such as the one located at coordinate $[3, 3]$, the resolution improves, which may lead to better accuracy. Building on this observation, the next figure investigates the accuracy of the proposed system for different values of SNR and varying OFDM parameterizations. Figure 5-4 shows the RMSE of the localisation for a single target, evaluated over SNR values ranging from -30 to 10 dB. The result was obtained from Monte Carlo simulations with 500 realizations. In each Monte Carlo realization, the target is randomly placed following a uniform distribution for both the x-axis and y-axis. Specifically,

it presents the results obtained for the regular deployment depicted in Figure 5-2 and the random deployment shown in Figure 5-3, for OFDM configurations with 64 and 256 subcarriers, respectively. The RMSE is computed using the following formula

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n ((x_i - \hat{x}_i)^2 + (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2)}, \quad (10)$$

where (x_i, y_i) represents the true position, (\hat{x}_i, \hat{y}_i) represents the estimated position, and n is the total number of realisations.

Figure 5-4: SNR versus RMSE for regular and random deployments, considering $K \in [64, 256]$.

The results in Figure 5-4 reveal two key trends. First, increasing the number of subcarriers from $K = 64$ to $K = 256$, while keeping the total bandwidth fixed, improves localisation accuracy in the low SNR regime. This improvement is due to the increased maximum unambiguous range provided by the finer subcarrier spacing at higher K , which helps mitigate range ambiguities. For instance, the RMSE starts to decrease at approximately -21 dB for $K = 256$, while for $K = 64$, the improvement begins around -16 dB. Second, for SNR values greater than roughly -5 dB, the RMSE plateaus and becomes primarily influenced by the spatial geometry of the antenna deployment rather than the noise level. In this regime, random deployments consistently outperform regular ones due to their enhanced geometric diversity, which helps reduce ambiguities and improve resolution. Conversely, the structured layout of the regular deployment results in more pronounced sidelobes and limits its localisation accuracy.

B. Scenario 2

This scenario considers a distributed MIMO radar system with one transmitter and one receiver, each equipped with a uniform linear array (ULA) of four antennas, with half-wavelength spacing. In such a scenario, we consider coherent signal processing at the CPU, assuming full phase synchronisation. For the radio-sensing channel, three targets are located at coordinates $[-1, -2]$, $[0, 0]$, and $[1, 1]$ meters. Figure 5-5 shows the radar image obtained using an interleaved OFDM signal with 256 subcarriers under two processing modes: (a) coherent and (b) non-coherent.

The comparison clearly demonstrates the benefits of coherent processing. From (a), we can notice that the use of ULAs at both ends and phase-aligned reconstruction across all channels results in a highly focused energy concentration at the actual target positions. In contrast, the non-coherent image in (b) reveals a high degree of ambiguity, preventing precise position localisation. The coherent fusion of all Tx–Rx pairs allows for the simultaneous estimation of range and angular position, a feature not present in the non-coherent case (b), which is limited to range estimation alone. This contrast

Figure 5-5: Radar imaging comparison for Scenario 2 under two processing modes: (a) coherent and (b) non-coherent.

confirms the improvement in localisation accuracy and resolution achieved through coherent processing.

Figure 5-6: Radar imaging comparison for Scenario 3 under two processing modes: (a) hybrid and (b) non-coherent processing, in which antennas are regularly deployed along the x- and y-axes.

C. Scenario 3

This scenario considers a distributed MIMO radar system with two transmitters and two receivers, each is equipped with a ULA of four half wavelength spaced antennas. The OFDM signal comprises 256 subcarriers. Three targets are located at positions $[-1, -2]$, $[0, 0]$, and $[1, 1]$ meters. In this hybrid configuration, coherent processing is performed within each terminal (leveraging intra-terminal

synchronisation), while non-coherent fusion is applied between terminals.

The key difference between scenarios 2 and 3 is the deployment of multiple Tx-Rx pairs in scenario 3. Figure 5-6(a) and Figure 5-6(b) show the image results for hybrid and non-coherent processing, respectively. Comparing these with Figure 5-5(b), which also employs non-coherent processing, highlights the limitation of single-Tx-Rx range estimation, higher ambiguity. On the other hand, the availability of multiple Tx-Rx pairs enables accurate estimation of the target position. With hybrid processing implemented, shown in Figure 5-6(a), the ability to estimate both range and angular position significantly diminishes image ambiguity.

In conclusion, compared to the other scenarios, hybrid processing offers a good compromise and emerges as the most effective trade-off solution, where it preserves some coherent gain while relaxing global synchronisation requirements, making it attractive for scalable distributed systems.

6 Wireless Self-Synchronisation

6.1 Motivation and Objectives

In this part of the work, within Task T4.1 of WP4, we investigate/present techniques to achieve wireless self-synchronisation when synchronisation signalling is not available (or in case of disruption of signalling cable) for some of the nodes involved in multistatic sensing operation. The work does not aim to outperform synchronisation proposed via optical signalling but to enable basic sensing operations which do not require precise synchronisation. Within this work, we are able to present new techniques for wireless self-synchronisation

1. Channel reciprocity-based algorithm to compensate time offset (TO) and CFO led by UCL,
2. TO compensation based on AoA, led by IMEC.

Both algorithms are applicable for wireless self-synchronisation in multistatic sensing operation within the framework of 6G-MUSICAL.

6.2 Channel Reciprocity Algorithm

6.2.1 Introduction

Accurate and reliable synchronisation is essential for both communication and sensing in a distributed JCAS system investigated in 6G-MUSICAL. Relying solely on optical clock distribution or GNSS for time and frequency synchronisation may not be feasible in complex environments, such as urban canyons or indoor settings, where the implementation of the wireline infrastructure is limited, or satellite signals can be obstructed. To ensure robust performance, distributed JCAS systems require over-the-air self-synchronisation techniques that maintain coordination without external references. Traditional over-the-air synchronisation methods depend on LoS links, but in many real-world scenarios, LoS links may be unavailable. To address this challenge, 6G-MUSICAL presents a novel synchronisation approach that leverages reflections from multiple objects or scatterers in the environment, which is a unique advantage of JCAS systems.

The method described here capitalizes on the fact that when two nodes observe the same objects from different positions, they experience timing and frequency shifts in a reciprocal manner, meaning the shifts are equal in magnitude but opposite in direction. This property is defined as offset reciprocity (OR). By exploiting OR, a high-accuracy synchronisation framework is developed, which compresses multiple reflected signals into a single offset value, enabling precise time and frequency alignment. This approach not only improves synchronisation accuracy but also eliminates the need for dedicated reference signals, making it a practical and scalable solution for distributed JCAS systems.

6.2.2 System Model

An OFDM signal is utilized for both wireless synchronisation and DL JCAS operations. To ensure clarity, the signal model follows a general OFDM framework, incorporating preambles, pilots, and JCAS signals, which include modulated communication data for transmission. This structured signal model enables over-the-air synchronisation while supporting seamless communication and sensing functions with the distributed JCAS system. The transmitted OFDM signal at the n th JCAS node in the distributed JCAS (D-JCAS) system is given by

$$s_n(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{P}} \sum_{q=0}^Q \sum_{p=0}^P X_n[p, q] \cdot \exp\left(j\left(2\pi(f_c + \delta_{f,n} + p\Delta f)(t - \delta_{t,n})\right)\right) \cdot \Pi\left(\frac{t - \delta_{t,n} - qT}{T}\right),$$

where P and Q represent the number of OFDM subcarriers and symbols, respectively. The term $X_n[p, q]$ denotes the (p, q) -th element of the modulated symbol matrix X_n . The carrier frequency is

denoted by f_c , while $\delta_{t,n}$ and $\delta_{f,n}$ represent the TO and CFO relative to a reference node. Without loss of generality, we set the reference node index as $n=1$. We assume that the transmitted sequences are fully orthogonal. Additionally, the cyclic prefix (CP) is omitted in this formulation, as CP removal during receiver processing prevents ISI.

In the frequency-domain representation, the received signal at the node n , which is transmitted from the other nodes and reflected by scatterers is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} Y_n &= \sum_{m=1}^N Y_{n,m} + Z_n, \\ Y_{n,m} &= H_{n,m} \odot X_m, \\ H_{n,m} &= \Lambda_{t,n,m} \Psi_{n,m} \Lambda_{f,n,m}, \end{aligned}$$

where \odot denotes the Hadamard product. $\Psi_{n,m}$ represents the true target channel matrix free from TO and CFO effects. $\Lambda_{t,n,m}$ and $\Lambda_{f,n,m}$ denote TO and CFO between nodes n and m , respectively. Also, Z_n is the AWGN at the node n . It is readily observed that the target channel $H_{n,m}$ includes the impact of TO and CFO, introducing distortions in target range and Doppler estimation unless properly compensated. To estimate a specific sensing channel $H_{n,m}$ from the received signal, the frequency-domain matched filtering is performed by using the transmitted signal from node m .

Figure 6-1: Illustration of reciprocal bistatic sensing links utilized for the proposed over-the-air time-frequency synchronisation.

6.2.3 Bistatic Channel Reciprocity based Fine-grained Synchronisation

In the proposed over-the-air synchronisation framework, OR in reciprocal bistatic sensing channels is utilised. Since multiple unknown reciprocal bistatic sensing links exist, as illustrated in Figure 6-1, these links can be leveraged to estimate TO and CFO between two JCAS nodes. The key principle is that while the actual target range and Doppler parameters in reciprocal bistatic links remain unchanged, the TO and CFO effects appear symmetrically in opposite directions, which is mathematically written as

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_{t,n,m} &= \Lambda_{t,m,n}^c, \\ \Lambda_{f,n,m} &= \Lambda_{f,m,n}^c, \end{aligned}$$

where c denotes the conjugate operator. This OR properties for TO and CFO allow us to estimate them without directly determining target parameters.

The proposed signal processing framework enables synchronisation by focusing solely on TO and CFO

estimation, regardless of the number of targets. Unlike traditional methods, it does not require prior knowledge of targets or the locations of JCAS nodes, making it a flexible and scalable solution for distributed JCAS systems. As a first step of the proposed technique before applying super-resolution estimators for TO and CFO estimation, we develop a bistatic signal matching (BSM) procedure to aggregate multiple scattered signals into a single offset for estimation.

The over-the-air synchronisation in distributed JCAS is implemented with the following steps:

- Delay-Doppler pre-processing to decouple delay and Doppler parameters for TO and CFO estimation. This reduces computational complexity compared to two-dimensional signal processing for joint TO and CFO estimation.
- BSM of the reciprocal bistatic measurements. It is implemented by the conjugate multiplication of the reciprocal bistatic signals in time domain (for TO) and frequency domain (for CFO).
- Apply super-resolution offset (SOE) estimators to get the fine-grained TO and CFO to the matched signals. Two different super-resolution estimators, maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) and matrix pencil (MP) approach, are developed. Here, they are denoted as SOE-MLE and SOE-MP, respectively.
- Compensate the estimated TO and CFO at the received sensing signals.

6.2.4 Results

The overall system parameters are set as follows: the OFDM signal bandwidth is 50 MHz, and the number of OFDM subcarriers and symbols are $P = 64$ and $Q = 32$, respectively. Since the proposed method is designed to provide fine-grained offset estimation and compensation, the standard deviations of the initial TO and CFO are set to 20 ns and 10 kHz, respectively. The bottom-line target localisation performance in noncoherent distributed JCAS is evaluated, which validates the effectiveness of the proposed over-the-air synchronisation.

Figure 6-2: Target localisation accuracy in distributed JCAS with varying time-offsets between nodes.

Figure 6-2 illustrates the impact of synchronisation on the target localisation performance in a distributed JCAS system for both centralized and decentralized processing. The analysis assumes that nodes are randomly deployed with a density of 100 nodes per square Km. In centralized processing, localisation is achieved by fusing signal-level data from all JCAS nodes. As a result, both N monostatic links and $(N^2 - N)$ bistatic links contribute to the target localisation process, leading to higher accuracy due to the increased number of measurements. For decentralized processing, each node performs target localisation independently. In this case, only the estimated TOFs from a single monostatic link and $(N - 1)$ bistatic links are combined for localisation. This approach reduces communication overhead but may result in lower localisation accuracy compared to centralized processing.

Figure 6-3: Target localisation accuracy vs. communication SINR trade-off: (left) Centralized and (right) decentralized processing.

Figure 6-4: Performance gain of D-JCAS with various wireless synchronisation approaches compared to the single-node JCAS system.

In the simulated results, centralised processing demonstrates more robust localisation performance against time synchronisation errors compared to decentralized processing. This is because monostatic measurements, which are unaffected by TO, help compensate for errors in bistatic measurements caused by TO. In the decentralized case, target localisation error increases proportionally with time synchronisation error. However, its impact decreases as the number of nodes grows. A larger number of nodes provides more independent bistatic measurements, increasing spatial diversity and enabling the JCAS system to mitigate synchronisation errors through the fusion of multiple bistatic measurements.

The D-JCAS trade-off performance obtained by applying different synchronisation techniques supports this analysis, as shown in Figure 6-3. The performance of decentralized processing is significantly affected by TO between JCAS nodes. With only a single monostatic link available, it cannot compensate for errors in bistatic measurements. Additionally, distributed JCAS performance using synchronisation based on spectral cross-correlation shows a noticeable performance gap compared to the case without synchronisation errors. This highlights the advantage of the proposed super-resolution offset estimation techniques, which enable fine-grained offset estimation for improved synchronisation accuracy.

D-JCAS improves target localisation by leveraging spatial diversity in distributed MIMO radar but is sensitive to synchronisation errors. Figure 6-4 compares noncoherent D-JCAS with a single-node JCAS system. When using the same number of antennas per node (denoted by M in the figure), D-JCAS

achieves better localisation accuracy and SINR due to power combining. However, a single-node JCAS system with an equivalent total number of antennas attains higher SINR due to coherent gain. While D-JCAS benefits from spatial diversity, spectral CC-based synchronisation (250 ps accuracy) prevents it from outperforming the single-node system. In contrast, the proposed SOE-MP technique (10 ps accuracy) provides enough cooperative sensing gain even with the decentralised processing.

6.2.5 Future Work

Future work of over-the-air synchronisation in WP4.1 involves investigating coherent D-JCAS systems, where distributed nodes achieve phase-level synchronisation to allow signals to add coherently at the communication receivers and the radar front-end. Such coherent designs could potentially unlock further gains in communication performance and improve parameter estimation accuracy. However, the challenge of mitigating phase noise and maintaining precise alignment across multiple geographically separated antennas is non-trivial. Advanced phase-tracking algorithms, hardware calibration, and robust synchronisation protocols would be needed to ensure reliable phase coherence, especially under real-time, dynamic operating conditions.

6.3 Angle-of-Arrival Intersection Algorithm

6.3.1 Introduction

JCAS has emerged as a technology to enable several applications envisioned for 6G and beyond [22], [23]. To exploit the wireless communication infrastructure for sensing, separate transmitter and receiver nodes not only avoid issues in full-duplex operation but also improve detection accuracy and extend the coverage area [24], [25]. Benefits associated with the multistatic sensing can be fully utilized if the stringent requirements of time and frequency synchronisation are achieved to ensure delay-Doppler consistency across nodes. Furthermore, accurate knowledge of node positioning and orientation are also important to preserve spatial coherence of sensing results [26].

A simple approach to provide common reference for time and frequency is through cables [27]. For example, the White Rabbit protocol distributes a highly stable reference through Ethernet connections, having the capability of achieving sub-nanosecond timing accuracy [28], which is suitable only for a limited number of nodes with limited separation distances. Therefore, for large scale systems, wireless synchronisation (often referred as synchronisation over the air) is important [29]. Existing wireless-based methods often require reference signals, dominant LoS path or a reference target for synchronisation, which limit the range of possible scenarios for sensing. For example, reference signals of the GNSS are used for timing synchronisation in [30], [31], with a reported accuracy of about 10–50 ns and for outdoor scenarios only. A technique based on LoS path and initial synchronisation by GNSS is presented in [32] which improves the timing synchronisation accuracy close to 0.1 ns. Use of GNSS reference timing for synchronisation not only limits the scenarios to outdoor but also demands additional hardware to enable nodes to receive GNSS signals. Other techniques use degree-of-freedom (DoF) in MIMO radars by increasing the number of radar modules [33].

These techniques are applicable if the nodes' locations are known, and targets are associated across the transmitter and receiver nodes. While accurate positions of nodes can be recorded at the time of installation, the association of targets across the transmitter and receiver nodes is challenging. Authors in [34] presented the channel reciprocity-based approach by introducing super-resolution in channel impulse response prior to channel cross correlation (CC). In channel reciprocity, transmitter and receiver switch their role in a bistatic pair to estimate channel impulse response and then CC among the estimated results is used to compensate the time and frequency offsets. Authors showed that improvement in synchronisation accuracy can be achieved beyond the conventional limit of time and frequency grid at the expense of high SNR. The method can provide fine-grained offset estimation

and requires an initial estimate for time and frequency offsets. In another work [35], authors exploited an additional DoF appearing in 2-D scenario where each target provides three independent parameters i.e., the bistatic distance, the angle-of-arrival (AoA) and the angle-of-departure (AoD), while only requiring two parameters (x, y) to be estimated. This provides one excess degree of freedom for each detected target, which allows the system offset parameters to be estimated. The work is limited to 2-D scenarios and requires AoD at receiver when applying AoD-AoA intersection approach for target localisation.

We propose a new technique for estimating the TO among transmitter and receiver nodes in multistatic sensing. This method uses AoA and delay estimates of targets, assuming known node locations and orientations. Any TO shifts the targets closer to or farther from the receiver nodes without impacting the AoAs. To overcome targets association at different nodes, we compute a mean of the targets' locations in 3-D space using possible TOs. Additionally, we use the transmitter-receiver separation delay as the minimum delay at which the nearest target can be detected. Finally, finding the delay which provides the minimum separation between the mean locations generated from different receiver nodes directly leads to compute time-offset compensation, under SNR conditions suitable for AoA estimation. Table 3 contains the list of important notations and their meaning.

6.3.2 System Model

In a multistatic sensing scenario involving a single transmitter T_x and L receiving nodes R_{x_i} where $i \in [1, L]$, we consider a bistatic pair with transmitter located at $\mathbf{p}_{T_x} = (x_{T_x}, y_{T_x}, z_{T_x})^T$ and i -th receiver located at $\mathbf{p}_{R_{x_i}} = (x_{R_{x_i}}, y_{R_{x_i}}, z_{R_{x_i}})^T$. The antenna array orientation is defined by $\Phi_{T_x} = (\theta_{T_x}, \phi_{T_x})^T$ for the transmitter and $\Phi_{R_{x_i}} = (\theta_{R_{x_i}}, \phi_{R_{x_i}})^T$ for the i -th receiver. We denote M and N as the number of antenna elements at the transmitter and receiver nodes respectively. Bistatic distance of a target located at point $\mathbf{p}_q = (x_q, y_q, z_q)^T$ is defined as,

$$d_q(x_q, y_q, z_q) = \|\mathbf{p}_{T_x} - \mathbf{p}_q\| + \|\mathbf{p}_q - \mathbf{p}_{R_{x_i}}\| \quad (1)$$

The AoA and AoD, associated with the q -th target, are denoted by $\Phi_{R_{x_i}, q} = (\theta_{R_{x_i}, q}, \phi_{R_{x_i}, q})^T$ and $\Phi_{T_x, q} = (\theta_{T_x, q}, \phi_{T_x, q})^T$, respectively. Figure 6-5 illustrates the configuration of a bistatic pair, including node orientations, locations, and the target's AoA and AoD.

Figure 6-5: Bistatic pair indicating nodes locations and orientations in a bistatic sensing.

Table 3: List of notations used in wireless self-synchronisation based on AoA intersection

Notation	Meaning	Notation	Meaning
T_x	Transmitter	τ_q^i	Delay associated with q -th target
L	Number of receiver nodes	α_q^i	Attenuation associated with q -th target
R_{x_i}	i -th receiver node	a_m	Transmit steering vector component for signal at the m -th antenna
$i \in [1, L]$	Index for the receiver node	b_n	Receive steering vector component for signal at the m -th antenna
\mathbf{p}_{T_x}	Position of the transmitter	$\epsilon_n^i(t)$	AWGN at the n -th antenna of the i -th receiver node
$\mathbf{p}_{R_{x_i}}$	Position of the i -th receiver node	c_0	Speed of light
Φ_{T_x}	Orientation of the transmitter	G_{T_x}	Transmitter antenna gain
θ_{T_x}	Azimuthal angle of Tx	$G_{R_{x_i}}$	Receiver antenna gain
φ_{T_x}	Elevation angle of Tx	f_c	Carrier frequency
$\Phi_{R_{x_i}}$	Orientation of the receiver i -th receiver node	T	OFDM symbol duration
$\theta_{R_{x_i}}$	Azimuthal angle of R_{x_i}	Δf	Sub-carrier spacing
$\varphi_{R_{x_i}}$	Elevation angle of R_{x_i}	T_s	OFDM symbol duration with CP
M	Number of antennas at the transmitter	T_{cp}	CP duration
N	Number of antennas at the receiver	\mathcal{M}	No. of OFDM symbols
\mathbf{p}_q	Location of the q -th target	\mathcal{N}	No. of subcarriers in one OFDM symbol
d_q	Bistatic distance of q -th target	μ	Index for OFDM symbols

$s_m(t)$	Transmit signal waveform at the m -th antenna	u	Index of sub-carriers
Q	Number of targets	$V_{n,m}^i(t)$	Baseband signal at the n -th antenna of i -th receiver node, transmitted from m -th antenna
$G = \mathcal{MN}$	Processing gain in 2-D FFT/IFFT operations	Θ_t	AoD, from a set of scanning range
γ^i	Detection threshold at the i -th receiver node	Θ_r	AoA, from a set of scanning range
$\Upsilon_{\text{Rx}_i,j}$	Polar coordinates of the j -th target at the i -th receiver node	$r_{\text{Rx}_i,j}$	Range associated with the j -th target
$R_{i,j}$	Range for the target from i -th receiver node	$k_{i,j}$	Discrete range bins from i -th receiver node
Δx_i	Separation of the Tx and the i -th receiver node along x-axis	T_{OF}	Time offset
Q_i	Number i -th receiver node	L	Range within the CP interval

If $s_m(t)$ represents the baseband signal, transmitted by the m -th antenna, which propagates through a radio channel consisting of Q number of distinct targets (modeled as point targets), then the received signal at the n -th antenna of node Rx_i can be expressed as,

$$y_{n,m}^i(t) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \alpha_q^i a_m(\Phi_{\text{Tx},q}) b_n(\Phi_{\text{Rx}_i,q}) s_m(t - \tau_q^i) + \epsilon_n^i(t) \quad (2)$$

here $\tau_q^i = (d_q^i - v_q^i t)/c_0$ is the propagation delay (c_0 , being the speed of light in free space), $a_m(\Phi_{\text{Tx},q})$ is the Tx steering vector component, $b_n(\Phi_{\text{Rx}_i,q})$ is the Rx_i steering vector component [36], v_q^i denotes the component of the speed of the q -th target which changes the bistatic distance, and $\epsilon_n^i(t)$ represents AWGN. α_q^i is the complex amplitude related to the q -th target,

$$\alpha_q^i = \sqrt{\frac{c_0^2 G_{\text{Tx}} G_{\text{Rx}_i} \sigma_q^i}{(4\pi)^3 \|p_{\text{Tx}} - p_q\|^2 \|p_q - p_{\text{Rx}_i}\|^2 f_c^2}} \quad (3)$$

Where in (3), σ_q^i is the radar cross-section of the q -th target, f_c is the carrier frequency, and G_{Tx} , G_{Rx_i} represent transmitting and receiving antenna gain, respectively.

A typical OFDM waveform $s_m(t)$ consists of several orthogonal subcarriers modulated by a set of data symbols and transmitted simultaneously after CP extension. The main purpose of CP is to avoid inter-

symbol-interference caused by the multipath radio channel and the CP length should be equal or larger than the delay spread of the radio channel. If the OFDM symbol duration is T , then the subcarrier spacing $\Delta f = \frac{1}{T}$ ensures the orthogonality among the subcarriers. We denote \mathcal{N} as the number of subcarriers, T_{cp} for CP interval, $T_s = T_{cp} + T$ the effective duration of the OFDM symbol, and \mathcal{M} as the total number of transmitted OFDM symbols. The transmitted OFDM waveform can be represented as [37],

$$s_m(t) = \sum_{\mu=0}^{\mathcal{M}-1} \sum_{u=0}^{\mathcal{N}-1} S(\mu\mathcal{N} + u) e^{(j2\pi u \Delta f (t - \mu T_s))} e^{(-j2\pi u \Delta f T_{cp})} \text{rect}\left(\frac{t - \mu T_s}{T_s}\right) e^{j2\pi f_c t} \quad (4)$$

where $S(\mu\mathcal{N} + u)$ is the data symbol which modulates the u -th subcarrier of the μ -th OFDM symbol. $\text{rect}(t)$ in (4) is the rectangular pulse shape and the term $e^{(-j2\pi u \Delta f T_{cp})}$ adjusts the initial phase of the subcarrier caused by the cyclic extension. Using (4) in (2), received signal takes the form

$$y_{n,m}^i(t) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \sum_{\mu=0}^{\mathcal{M}-1} \sum_{u=0}^{\mathcal{N}-1} \alpha_q^i a_m(\Phi_{\text{Tx},q}) b_n(\Phi_{\text{Rx},i,q}) S(\mu\mathcal{N} + u) e^{(j2\pi u \Delta f (t - \tau_q^i - \mu T_s - T_{cp}))} \cdot e^{(j2\pi f_c (t - \tau_q^i))} \text{rect}\left(\frac{t - \tau_q^i - \mu T_s}{T_s}\right) + \epsilon_n^i(t). \quad (5)$$

The subcarrier spacing Δf is usually chosen at least order of magnitude higher than the possible Doppler shift, to avoid any considerable loss of orthogonality among the subcarriers, therefore the overall Doppler shift is considered as caused by the carrier frequency f_c .

After down-conversion the baseband equivalent of (5) is,

$$V_{n,m}^i(t) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \sum_{\mu=0}^{\mathcal{M}-1} \sum_{u=0}^{\mathcal{N}-1} \hat{\alpha}_q^i a_m(\Phi_{\text{Tx},q}) b_n(\Phi_{\text{Rx},i,q}) S(\mu\mathcal{N} + u) e^{(j2\pi u \Delta f (t - \tau_q^i - \mu T_s - T_{cp}))} \cdot e^{(j2\pi f_c (t v_q^i / c_0))} \text{rect}\left(\frac{t - \tau_q^i - \mu T_s}{T_s}\right) + \hat{\epsilon}_n^i(t), \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{\alpha}_q^i = \alpha_q^i e^{(-j2\pi f_c d_q^i)}$ and $\hat{\epsilon}_n^i(t) = \epsilon_n^i(t) e^{(-j2\pi f_c t)}$. Finally, the signal $V_{n,m}^i(t)$ is sampled and, after removal of the CP, converted into the frequency domain by using a DFT typically implemented by a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT),

$$A_{n,m}^i(\mu\mathcal{N} + u) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \hat{\alpha}_q^i a_m(\Phi_{\text{Tx},q}) b_n(\Phi_{\text{Rx},i,q}) S(\mu\mathcal{N} + u) e^{(j2\pi u \Delta f \tau_q^i)} \cdot e^{(j2\pi f_c (t v_q^i / (c_0 \mu T_s))} + Z_n^i(\mu\mathcal{N} + u), \quad (7)$$

where $A_{n,m}^i(\mu\mathcal{N} + u)$ is the received data symbol (affected by the channel and AWGN) at the u -th subcarrier of the μ -th OFDM symbol at the n -th receiving antenna, and $Z_n^i(\mu\mathcal{N} + u)$ is the frequency domain equivalent of $\hat{\epsilon}_n^i(t)$.

2-D FFT Based Sensing

For sensing, the received signal $A_{n,m}^i(\mu\mathcal{N} + u)$ is divided by the transmitted data symbols $S(\mu\mathcal{N} + u)$ and applying IFFT operation (along subcarriers) results in peaks corresponding to delay τ_q^i ,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{r}_{n,m}^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) &= \sum_{q=1}^Q \hat{\alpha}_q^i a_m(\Phi_{Tx,q}) b_n(\Phi_{Rx_i,q}) \\ &\quad \cdot \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} \sum_{u=0}^{\mathcal{N}-1} e^{(j2\pi u \Delta f \tau_q^i)} e^{(j2\pi u \boldsymbol{\kappa} / \mathcal{N})} \\ &\quad \cdot e^{(j2\pi f_c (t v_q^i / (c_0 \mu T_s)))} + \hat{Z}_n^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Where $\boldsymbol{\kappa} = (0, \dots, \mathcal{N} - 1)$ defines the range grid in the RD map, and $\hat{Z}_n^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ represents the noise part. Afterwards, an FFT operation is applied along the slow-time (index μ) to the Doppler estimate,

$$\hat{r}_{n,m}^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\varkappa}) = \sum_{\mu=0}^{\mathcal{M}-1} \hat{r}_{n,m}^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) e^{-j2\pi\mu/\mathcal{M}} e^{(j2\pi\mu\boldsymbol{\kappa}/\mathcal{N})} \quad (9)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varkappa} = (0, \dots, \mathcal{M} - 1)$ defines the Doppler grid in RD map.

The IFFT/FFT operations, for range and speed detection, provide processing gain $G = \mathcal{M}\mathcal{N}$ due to coherent addition of signals. The orthogonality, associated with the discrete frequencies of the complex exponentials in IFFT/FFT operations, can not be guaranteed for range and speed which causes delay-Doppler leakages resulting in sidelobes in the RD map. These sidelobes are often suppressed by using windowing prior to IFFT/FFT operations.

Subsequently, after combining across antenna dimensions yields

$$\begin{aligned} \rho^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\varkappa}, \Theta_t, \Theta_r) &= \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \hat{r}_{n,m}^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\varkappa}) (\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\varkappa}) w_m(\Theta_t) v_n(\Theta_r) \\ &= \sum_{q=1}^Q \hat{\alpha}_q^i \chi_q(\Theta_t) \Psi_q(\Theta_r) \\ &\quad \cdot \sum_{\mu=0}^{\mathcal{M}-1} \sum_{u=0}^{\mathcal{N}-1} \left(e^{j2\pi u \Delta f \tau_q^i} e^{j \frac{2\pi}{\mathcal{N}} u \boldsymbol{\kappa}} \right) \left(e^{j2\pi f_c t \frac{v_q^i}{c_0 \mu T_s}} e^{-j2\pi \frac{\mu}{\mathcal{M}} \boldsymbol{\varkappa}} \right) + \epsilon(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \Theta_t, \Theta_r) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_q(\Theta_t) &= \sum_{m=1}^M a_m(\Phi_{Tx,q}) w_m(\Theta_t) \\ \Psi_q(\Theta_r) &= \sum_{n=1}^N b_n(\Phi_{Rx_i,q}) v_n(\Theta_r) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where Θ_t and Θ_r are taken from a set of values that cover the scanning range of AoD and AoA, respectively. In the case of beamforming, the filters $w_m(\Theta_t)$ and $v_n(\Theta_r)$ are chosen as the complex conjugate of the steering vectors $a_m(\Phi_{Tx,q})$ and $b_n(\Phi_{Rx_i,q})$, respectively.

Finally, detection is performed based on the results $\rho^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\varkappa}, \Theta_t, \Theta_r)$, under a predefined threshold value

$$|\rho^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\varkappa}, \Theta_t, \Theta_r)|^2 \geq \gamma^i \quad (12)$$

where the threshold value γ^i is set against the probability of false alarm detection. We will use $(\kappa_j^i, \kappa_j^i, \Theta_{t,j}^i, \Theta_{r,j}^i)$ as the j -th set of values which satisfy (12), hence representing j -th detected target at the i -th receiver node Rx_i .

6.3.3 Algorithm Description

Let $Q_i \leq Q$ represents the number of detected targets at the i -th receiving node Rx_i as shown Figure 6-6. We assume

Q targets reflecting towards all receiving nodes; however, due to the bistatic geometry, some targets may fall into the same range bin, leading to differences in the size of the list of detected targets across receiving nodes. The polar coordinates of the j -th detected target at the i -th receiving node Rx_i are denoted as $Y_{Rx_i,j} = (r_{Rx_i,j}, \hat{\theta}_{Rx_i,j}, \hat{\phi}_{Rx_i,j})$, where

$$r_{Rx_i,j} = c_0 \kappa_j^i (T/\mathcal{N}) \quad (13)$$

And $\Theta_{r,j}^i = [\hat{\theta}_{Rx_i,j}, \hat{\phi}_{Rx_i,j}]$. As depicted in Figure 6-6, $r_{Rx_i,j}$ does not represent the actual range $R_{i,j}$ of the target, instead, it includes an excess part $\Delta R_{i,j}$, which depends on the geometry of the bistatic pair and must be subtracted from $r_{Rx_i,j}$. In case of a monostatic setup, $r_{Rx_i,j}$ is simply twice the actual range $R_{i,j}$ which can be calculated directly.

Figure 6-6: Relation of the bistatic geometry with the range of the target.

Using the transmitter position p_{Tx} , the receiver position p_{Rx_i} and the polar coordinates $Y_{i,j}$, the excess range $\Delta R_{i,j}$ can be determined using the following relation (a derivation for 2-D case is provided in [35], which we extend to the 3-D case here),

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta R_{i,j} = & \left\{ (\Delta T_{i,j})^2 + (\Delta x_i)^2 + (\Delta y_i)^2 + (\Delta z_i)^2 + 2\Delta T_{i,j} (\Delta x_i \cos(\theta_{Rx_i} - \hat{\theta}_{Rx_i,j}) \right. \\ & \cdot \sin(\phi_{Rx_i} - \hat{\phi}_{Rx_i,j}) + \Delta y_i \sin(\theta_{Rx_i} - \hat{\theta}_{Rx_i,j}) \cos(\phi_{Rx_i} - \hat{\phi}_{Rx_i,j}) \\ & \left. + \Delta z_i \sin(\phi_{Rx_i} - \hat{\phi}_{Rx_i,j}) \right\}^{1/2} \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\Delta T_{i,j} = \frac{(r_{Rx_i,j})^2 - (\Delta x_i)^2 - (\Delta y_i)^2 - (\Delta z_i)^2}{2 \left(\left(r_{Rx_i,j} + \Delta x_i \cos(\theta_{Rx_i} - \theta_{Rx_i,j}) \cos(\phi_{Rx_i} - \phi_{Rx_i,j}) \right) \right)} \quad (15)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta x_i &= x_{Rx_i} - x_{Tx} \\
\Delta y_i &= y_{Rx_i} - y_{Tx} \\
\Delta z_i &= z_{Rx_i} - z_{Tx}
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

In the case where Tx and Rx_i are collocated (monostatic setup), i.e., $\Delta x_i = 0$, $\Delta y_i = 0$, $\Delta z_i = 0$, the excess range $\Delta R_{i,j}$ simplifies to $\Delta R_{i,j} = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) r_{Rx_i,j}$ which can be easily verified from (14), (15). Once $\Delta R_{i,j}$ is determined, the actual range of the j -th target is as

$$R_{i,j} = r_{Rx_i,j} - \Delta R_{i,j} \tag{17}$$

In order to convert the local polar coordinates at receiver node Rx_i into the global Cartesian coordinate $(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}, z_{i,j})^T$ the knowledge of the location and orientation of the receiver node is used as follows. First, use the orientation of the receiver node Rx_i and convert the polar coordinates $(R_{i,j}, \hat{\theta}_{Rx_i,j} + \theta_{Rx_i}, \hat{\phi}_{Rx_i,j} - \phi_{Rx_i})^T$ into Cartesian coordinates $(\hat{x}_{i,j}, \hat{y}_{i,j}, \hat{z}_{i,j})^T$, and then using the location of the receiver mode to get the target position in global coordinates as $\mathbf{p}_{i,j}$ as

$$\mathbf{p}_{i,j} = (\hat{x}_{i,j} + x_{Rx_i}, \hat{y}_{i,j} + y_{Rx_i}, \hat{z}_{i,j} + z_{Rx_i})^T \tag{18}$$

Any TO between the Tx and Rx_i will affect $r_{Rx_i,j}$ without altering the AoA estimates. Since $r_{Rx_i,j}$ cannot be less than the distance d_{Tx}^i the Tx and Rx_i as a first step in the proposed wireless time-synchronisation, we define $k_{i,j}$ as

$$k_{i,j} = d_{Tx}^i + r_{Rx_i,j} - \min_j(r_{Rx_i,j}) \quad j \in [1, Q_i] \tag{19}$$

and use $k \in [k_{i,j}, L]$ in place of $r_{Rx_i,j}$ in (14), (15), and (17) to generate possible sets of Q_i targets due to TO error, where L is the range covered by the CP. Next, we generate a mean location $\mathbf{S}_{i,k}$ of the detected targets for different value k,

$$\mathbf{S}_{i,k} = \left(\frac{1}{Q_i}\right) \sum_{j=1}^{Q_i} \mathbf{p}_{i,j}^k \tag{20}$$

where $\mathbf{p}_{i,j}^k$ represents the position (Cartesian coordinates) of a target using k. Figure 6-7 illustrates the main idea of generating these mean locations $\mathbf{S}_{i,k}$ with the help of a multistatic sensing scenario employing one Tx and three receiver nodes. Four targets (red crosses) are detected independently by each of the receiver node using different values of k (one set of black dots connected by black line represents sensing results of the node for one value of k and their mean location $\mathbf{S}_{i,k}$ is drawn by color dots). In Figure 6-7, for representation clarity, only mean locations are shown after a few sets of detected targets.

Figure 6-7: Illustration of the proposed idea of wireless self-synchronisation in multistatic sensing.

Next step is to find the minimum distance among $S_{i,k}$ of different receiving nodes i.e.,

$$\hat{k}_{i,l} = \arg \min_k \|S_{i,k} - S_{l,g}\|_2 \quad g \in [k_l, L] \text{ and } i \neq l \quad (21)$$

Where $\hat{k}_{i,l}$ is the value of k at the i -th receiver node Rx_i which brings the mean location closest to a mean location of the l -th receiver node. The estimate of the mean-range is calculated by averaging the results i.e.,

$$\hat{R}_i = \frac{1}{L-1} \sum_{e=1}^L \hat{k}_{i,e} \quad (22)$$

The time-offset T_{OF} of the i -th receiving node is calculated as

$$T_{OF} = \frac{1}{Q_i} \sum_{j=1}^{Q_i} \frac{R_{i,j}}{c_0} - \frac{\hat{R}_i}{c_0} \quad (23)$$

Where the first part on the right side of (23) is the delay associated with the mean of the targets detected initially, without applying the proposed method for estimating the TO.

6.3.4 Results

To numerically validate the proposed time-synchronisation method, we employ a multistatic scenario with one transmitter and four receiver nodes which are oriented to cover a common geographical region. A time-domain signal is generated using 512 subcarriers (FFT size), with 212 subcarriers nulled (106 guard band subcarriers on one side, 105 guard band subcarriers on the other side and a DC null) and the remaining 300 active subcarriers modulated with 16-QAM data symbols. The signal undergoes an IFFT operation with a sampling frequency of 1 GHz and is extended with a CP of 128 samples length before transmission. At each receiver node, RD processing is performed using the conventional two-dimensional IFFT/FFT method and beamforming to detect targets according to (12). Accurate AoA estimation is carried out using well known 2-D MUSIC algorithm [38]. The receiver nodes are equipped with rectangular antenna arrays with half-wavelength spacing, and the transmitter with a ULA along the z -axis. Key parameters are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: List of simulation parameters for wireless self-synchronisation based on AoA

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Number of nodes involved in multistatic sensing	5	Sampling frequency F_s	1 GHz
Cartesian coordinates of Tx	[0,0,0]	Carrier frequency f_c	6 GHz
Orientation of Tx	[0,0]	Active sub-carriers	300
Cartesian coordinates of Rx1	[10,4,0]	FFT size	512
Orientation of Rx1	[180,0]	Subcarrier spacing Δf	1.953 MHz
Cartesian coordinates of Rx2	[10,-4,0]	Bandwidth	586 MHz
Orientation of Rx2	[180,0]	Digital mapping	16 QAM
Cartesian coordinates of Rx3	[4,4,0]	No. of OFDM symbols	16
Orientation of Rx3	[0,0]	Range resolution	0.256 m
Cartesian coordinates of Rx4	[4,-4,0]	Monostatic range (within CP)	16.38 m
Orientation of Rx4	[0,0]		

Signal propagation is modelled using a geometrical channel approach, which accounts for the locations

of the nodes and point targets. Figure 6-8 shows 3-D view of the multi-sensing with different arrangements of targets along with mean location (coloured dots matched in colour with nodes). Figure 6-8(a) shows the proposed mean point intersection for four targets in a line formation, Figure 6-8(b) is a snapshot of the scenario when four targets are randomly located. Furthermore, Figure 6-8(c) is taken for a single target to show the applicability of the proposed method for a single target (where mean location is the same as the detected location). It is important to note that the spacing between the mean locations is not uniform. For example, in Figure 6-8(a), mean location of the detected targets at the 1st receiver node (red dots) show larger spacing difference compared to the mean locations from the 4th indicating suitability of one bistatic pair (Tx-targets- R_{x_4}) over other bistatic pair (Tx-targets- R_1).

Figure 6-8: AoA based wireless self-synchronisation with different arrangement of targets.

For the performance evaluation of the proposed method, random values (within CP interval) are set for TO between the transmitter and the receiver nodes for 100 iterations. In each iteration, a waveform of 16 OFDM symbols is transmitted through a channel constructed by four targets, randomly located in the coverage region. Figure 6-9 shows the RMSE performance of the proposed technique compared to the channel CC approach for different SNR values. With a baseband bandwidth of 586 MHz, we are able to get a time synchronisation accuracy around 1 ns. While the CC method performs slightly better than the proposed method but requires cooperation from the transmitter for each bistatic pair, whereas the proposed method does not require such assistance from the transmitter. Results for Rx_1 and Rx_2 differ slightly from results for Rx_3 and Rx_4 , indicating their dependence on positions of the nodes in the multistatic scenario. As the proposed TO estimation is grid based (grid resolution inversely proportional to the signal bandwidth), improvement in estimation accuracy can be achieved by increasing the signal bandwidth.

Figure 6-9: Performance of the AoA based wireless self-synchronisation method.

6.3.5 *Future Work*

The algorithm will be investigated for other scenarios where a group of detected targets will be used (relaxing the condition that all the targets are detected by all the nodes involved in multistatic sensing). Additionally, a reflector of opportunity based wireless self-synchronisation will also be investigated, where a target, whose coordinates are known to the sensing receiver nodes, will be utilized to compensate synchronisation error.

7 Node Precise Clock and Carrier Frequency Synchronisation

7.1 Introduction

In current RANs, clock synchronisation and RF carrier generation/synchronisation are treated as separate problems, each addressed using separate devices and systems. For example, current clock synchronisation in RANs uses Synchronous Ethernet (Sync-E) [11] and the PTP [39], which only achieves ns-level clock precision, is insufficient for the demand for cm-level positioning that requires <30ps clock precision. Although GNSS can achieve ps-level timing accuracy, their performance is limited by LoS requirements and susceptibility to jamming and spoofing, due to the inherently weak satellite signals [40].

Conventional RF signal generation relies on electronic phase-locked loops (PLLs). However, PLLs occupy substantial silicon area, consume high power, and exhibit phase noise that increases quadratically with frequency. These limitations present significant barriers to deploying low phase noise, phase-synchronized RF carriers in ultra-dense cellular networks, where tight timing coordination across multiple RUs is crucial.

In this work, we propose and experimentally demonstrate a unified and scalable solution for both ps-level clock synchronisation and phase-synchronized RF carrier generation using a single ultra-low noise optical frequency comb (OFC). Building on our previous demonstrations of clock phase caching for ps-level timing over point-to-point links [41], and low phase noise RF carrier generation across wide frequency bands using optoelectronic frequency combs [42], we now combine both techniques into a single proof-of-concept point-to-multipoint RAN architecture. Specifically,

1. we use the Menhir femtosecond laser at the DU as a master comb source with 2.5 GHz spacing, serving both as a clock reference and as a generator of multiple RF carriers after photodetection,
2. distribute this optical comb to all RUs via optical fibre, multiplexed with data signals
3. demonstrate clock phase caching to efficiently compensate for one-way fibre-induced clock phase drift, avoiding the complexity of traditional bi-directional fibre noise cancellation schemes.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first demonstration of combined ps-level clock synchronisation and ultra-low phase noise RF carrier distribution in a unified system. This enables robust, scalable, and low-cost architectures for next-generation RANs, supporting high-accuracy positioning, distributed beamforming, and low-jitter carrier distribution.

7.2 Low Phase Noise Carrier Frequency Synchronisation

This section describes the system architecture for achieving both picosecond-level clock synchronisation and phase-synchronized RF carrier generation using a single ultra-low noise OFC. At the core of the system is the Menhir-1550 femtosecond laser, which acts as a common optical clock and is directly used for RF carrier generation after photodetection. We outline the high-level system design and present the optical and RF characterisation of the Menhir comb, confirming its suitability as a stable, low-jitter timing and frequency source for synchronised multi-RU deployments.

7.2.1 High Level Description

Figure 7-1 presents a conceptual architecture of the proposed for the clock and carrier-synchronised RAN. The design enables precise, low-cost distribution of timing and RF signals from a central DU to

multiple RUs via optical fibre.

At the heart of the system is a Menhir femtosecond OFC with a 2.5 GHz line spacing, generated at the DU. Selected comb lines are filtered using an optical bandpass filter (OBPF) to mitigate the effect of chromatic dispersion introduced by the transmission fibre on the comb lines, an issue further investigated in a later section. An alternative solution to combat dispersion is the use of dispersion compensation modules (DCMs), which are designed to reverse the accumulated dispersion in long fibre links. However, in this work, we explore the use of optical filtering as a flexible and scalable approach to managing dispersion while preserving the spectral integrity of the frequency comb. These filtered comb lines are then wavelength-division multiplexed (WDM) with data signals and transmitted simultaneously to all RUs.

Figure 7-1: Concept of optical comb and data co-transmission from DU with co-reception at radio units (by a single photodiode).

At the RU, the comb signal is demultiplexed, split and recombined with data signals before sending to each RU via feeder fibres. As a result, each photodiode (PD) will simultaneously detect both comb signal and data signal. With a comb-data wavelength separation higher than the PD bandwidth, the PD will generate an RF comb, with a spacing equal to that of the optical comb tones (f_{rep}) [43] and overlaid atop the data. Analogue filtering is used to extract clock, data and RF carrier, enabling single PD reception for low-cost RUs.

As shown in Figure 7-1, optical fibre introduces $+\delta\varphi(t)$ of slow clock phase drift from temperature change per direction (about $39 \text{ ps}/(\text{km} \cdot \text{K})$) for standard single-mode fibre (SSMF) [44]. With the RU upstream transmitter driven by the disseminated clock, we effectively build a clock return link that permits cancellation of fibre induced clock phase shift. The 2-way change in clock phase offset, $+2\delta\varphi(t)$, of data arriving from the RU at the DU is measured at the phase update rate of f_φ . Updates are sent to the RU at the same rate, which corrects the phase of its data sent to the DU by $-2\delta\varphi(t)$ at f_φ , cancelling the fibre clock phase shift of the RU to DU data. The RU also corrects for the 1-way clock shift, $+\delta\varphi(t)$, by halving the measured 2-way clock shift to $-\delta\varphi(t)$, cancelling the 1-way clock shift $+\delta\varphi(t)$ in the outbound path, in turn clock phase synchronising the RU's clock to the DU's clock.

7.2.2 Optical Clock Source Characterisation

This section focuses on the characterization of the MENHIR-1550 femtosecond laser, which serves as the high-precision optical clock source for our system. It generates ultra-stable 2.5 GHz pulse trains with exceptionally low timing jitter of 18.2 fs and amplitude noise (0.01%), providing a reliable foundation for both clock synchronisation and RF carrier generation. The laser operates at 1551.1 nm with 755 fs pulses, and it also features piezoelectric tuning for fine control of its repetition rate. Its robust performance (28.2 mW output, integrated monitoring, and low-noise design) makes it ideal for

applications requiring exact timing.

The subsections that follow detail the experimental characterization of the comb in both the optical and RF domains, confirming its spectral integrity, stability, and suitability for use as a common clock and RF source in synchronized multi-unit systems.

7.2.2.1 RF characterization

The RF characterization of the Menhir MLL is performed using the experimental setup shown in Figure 7-2, which includes a variable optical attenuator (VOA), a photodetector (PD), and a phase noise analyser. The setup enables measurement of RF tones generated via photodetection of the OFC, with frequency components spaced by the laser’s 2.5 GHz repetition rate. However, due to the bandwidth

Figure 7-2: Schematic of the experimental setup used for comb characterization in RF domain.

limitation of the photodetector, this configuration supports RF signal analysis up to 40 GHz.

Figure 7-3: The RF spectra of the 2.5G, 5G and 10 GHz tones.

Figure 7-4: The SFDR and sub-harmonic line spacing vs. signal frequency of Menhir MLL comb.

The phase noise analyser employs a combination of cross-correlation and fast Fourier transform (FFT) techniques to extract the phase noise spectrum of each RF tone. Measurements are conducted over a wide range of frequency offsets from the carrier, and the results are expressed in dBc/Hz (decibels relative to the carrier per Hertz), as is standard in phase noise analysis.

Figure 7-3 shows the measured RF spectra of individual comb lines of the Menhir MLL at 2.5GHz, 10 GHz and 20 GHz. The spectral representation of individual tones from the Menhir MLL displays distinct narrow linewidths peaks with noticeable sub-harmonics accompanying each tone. These sub-harmonic components create a symmetrical, mirror-like pattern around the centre frequency. The presence of the sub-harmonics suggests potential nonlinear effects or modulation artifacts within the laser system. Despite their presence, the harmonics remain at low power levels relative to the carriers, which is reflected in the high spurious-free dynamic range (SFDR) values observed across the measured tones.

Figure 7-4 presents the measured SFDR for selected RF tones at 2.5 GHz, 5 GHz, 10 GHz, and 20 GHz, along with the corresponding line spacing between each primary tone and its nearest sub-harmonics. The SFDR remains above 85 dB, indicating excellent spectral purity and low interference from spurious components. The line spacing between sub-harmonics and their carriers is consistently measured between 450 kHz and 500 kHz, suggesting a stable modulation pattern likely linked to laser dynamics or photodetection effects.

Figure 7-5: Phase noise measurements for selected comb tones are presented.

Figure 7-5 shows the single-sideband (SSB) phase noise power spectral density (PSD) measured for different RF tones generated by the Menhir MLL at 2.5 GHz, 5 GHz, 10 GHz, 20 GHz, and 40 GHz, measured over an offset frequency range from 10 Hz to 30 MHz. As expected, the phase noise decreases with increasing offset frequency, exhibiting a characteristic slope indicative of different noise regimes, such as flicker noise and white phase noise.

- In the **low offset frequency range** (10 Hz to 100 kHz), the phase noise exhibits a steep decline, typically following a $1/f^2$ to $1/f^3$ slope indicating the dominance of random frequency noise and flicker noise, arising from long-term, correlated fluctuations within the laser system.
- **At offsets above ~100 kHz**, the phase noise begins to flatten, forming a white noise floor for each comb line. This flat behaviour indicates that the phase noise becomes independent of offset frequency, which is characteristic of white phase noise. In this regime, the dominant noise sources are typically shot noise and thermal noise, originating from the quantum randomness of photon detection at the PD. All the comb lines, from 2.5 GHz up to 20 GHz, converge toward a similar noise floor around -150 dBc/Hz, suggesting that the system is likely

shot-noise-limited at high offsets. Whereas the 40 GHz tone exhibits higher noise due to detector bandwidth limitations and increased system noise at high frequencies. A distinct peak appears around 500 kHz is observed across all tones, which corresponds to the sub-harmonic spectral features seen in Figure 7-3.

These results confirm the low phase noise and high spectral stability of the Menhir comb, validating its use as a high-quality clock and RF source in synchronised systems.

7.2.2.2 Optical Characterisation

The optical characterisation of the Menhir MLL comb aims to assess the spectral structure and phase stability of the generated OFC. To benchmark its performance, we compare the Menhir comb with a high-stability

Figure 7-6: a) Experimental setup for optical line by line phase noise measurement. Conceptual diagrams of the line-by-line measurement procedure, demonstrating (b) optical and (c) electrical filtering; light and dark blue peaks represent tones, Menhir Comb.

2.5 GHz electro-optic (EO) comb generated via intensity and phase modulation of a continuous-wave laser.

Figure 7-6 illustrates the experimental setup used for this optical phase noise comparison. The comparison is performed using a heterodyne detection system, which enables line-by-line phase noise characterisation of the Menhir comb across a 6 nm optical bandwidth centred at 1551.62 nm. To benchmark its performance, the Menhir comb was compared against a high-stability 25 GHz EO frequency comb generated by intensity and phase modulation of a continuous-wave laser. The EO comb is generated by modulating a seed laser with a Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM) followed by a phase modulator (PMod), both driven by a 25 GHz RF synthesizer. The EO comb is combined with the Menhir MLL comb using a 50:50 coupler, filtered through an OBPF, and photo-detected. The resulting heterodyne beat signals are amplified and passed through a low-pass filter (LPF) before being analysed using a phase noise analyser. This configuration enables high-resolution spectral comparison of individual comb lines from each source.

Figure 7-7 shows a segment of the optical spectra, with the Menhir Photonics comb overlaid on the EO comb. Differences in resolution bandwidths used during measurement are reflected in the split vertical axes, and central frequencies are highlighted for reference. A zoomed-in view near the Menhir comb's central wavelength (1551.62 nm) illustrates its spectral detail.

Figure 7-7: Comparison of Optical Spectra from Menhir Photonics and EO Frequency Combs.

Figure 7-8: (a) Phase noise measurements (b) frequency noise measurements for a selection of tones of the 6 nm sweep range. The inset in (a) demonstrates a zoomed in portion of the phase noise spectra (1 to 2 kHz range). The left (black) axis of the second inset in (b) demonstrates the combined optical spectra of both Menhir comb and EO comb; the right (red axis indicated the average optical power input to the photodiode, with the EO (crosses) and without the EO comb.

A complete line-by-line phase noise characterisation of the Menhir Photonics MLL was achieved using a high-stability 25 GHz EO frequency comb as a reference oscillator. The heterodyne detection system enabled precise measurement of phase noise PSD across a 6 nm bandwidth centred at 1551.62 nm, revealing three distinct noise regimes with specific characteristics.

- Low-Frequency Domain (10^2 – 10^5 Hz):** In this regime, the phase noise is dominated by random frequency noise ($S \propto f^{-4}$: $10^2 < f < 10^5$), exhibiting a characteristic -20 dB/decade slope. The measured phase noise amplitude reaches approximately 1 rad²/Hz at 1 kHz offset, as shown in the inset of Figure 7-8(a). Integration of the noise profile suggests a sub-kHz Lorentzian linewidth contribution, highlighting the laser's intrinsic stability.
- Crossover Region (~500 kHz):** A pronounced peak at ~500 kHz is attributed to relaxation oscillations in the MLL's gain medium, introducing an additional 3-5 dB of phase noise above the baseline. This technical noise floor effectively limits the achievable Lorentzian linewidth to the 1-10 kHz range, representing a key factor in the laser's performance for precision

applications. The presence of this peak underscores the importance of gain medium dynamics in the overall noise budget.

- **High-Frequency Domain (>1 MHz):** At higher frequencies, white phase noise ($S \propto f^0: f > 10^6$) becomes dominant, with the noise floor reaching -120 dBc/Hz at 1 MHz offset. This regime is primarily influenced by the RF synthesizer driving the EO comb, which exhibits 15 fs of integrated jitter. The system's EDFA also contributes an additional 20 dB of noise above the seed laser reference, setting a practical limit on the resolvable linewidth in this frequency range.
- **Spectral Uniformity and System Performance:** The measurements demonstrate excellent spectral uniformity, with less than 1 rad²/Hz variation in phase noise across comb lines at offsets below 10⁴ Hz. Optical power variations among the 15 measured tones remain below 0.5 dB, confirming consistent mode-to-mode coherence—a critical requirement for wavelength-division multiplexed systems. The total optical power incident on the photodetector increased by 0.4 dBm over the 6 nm sweep range, reflecting the system's stability during characterisation.
- **Measurement Limitations and Artefacts:** Several factors constrained the ultimate resolution of the measurements. Amplifier saturation introduced artefacts at ~700 kHz, which were removed during post-processing. Residual RF synthesizer noise, scaling across the 50 kHz–12 MHz range, further limited high-frequency accuracy. Optical constraints included the 30 GHz bandpass filter's transmission non-uniformity and the need to power-match the local oscillator to the weakest comb tone. The system's thermal noise floor was estimated at -140 dBc/Hz, with the 5 GHz photodetector and single EDFA configuration imposing additional practical limits. This analysis provides the first complete characterization of the 2.5 GHz Menhir frequency comb, demonstrating its suitability for applications requiring sub-kHz linewidth stability, such as PON and RAN synchronisation systems. The results highlight both the laser's inherent noise properties and the measurement system's capabilities and limitations.

7.3 Narrow-Band Comb Filtering Techniques for Power Fading Mitigation

One of the key challenges in utilising the Menhir comb is power fading caused by chromatic dispersion during fibre transmission. Chromatic dispersion in optical fibres introduces phase shifts across all OFC lines, resulting in constructive or destructive interference of the generated RF signals [45]. This interference can lead to significant power loss of individual comb lines at certain transmission distances, which in turn deteriorates the power of the distributed RF carrier to different RUs.

Previous studies have proposed simplified models to characterise this power fading effect and have suggested using a waveshaper to pre-compensate for fibre dispersion [46], [47]. However, these approaches typically focus only on the first RF comb line and require recalibration of the dispersion compensation for different transmission lengths. Another study measured RF comb power at two separate transmission distances, but it did not provide a detailed relationship between dispersion and the power of higher-order RF comb lines.

In our previous work, we developed a model to quantify the impact of chromatic dispersion on the power of RF frequency combs. Building on this model, we proposed and demonstrated the use of optical spectrum shaping to mitigate dispersion-induced power fading. Further details on this work can be found in [41].

Power fading in OFC transmission over fibre arises primarily from chromatic dispersion and the nature of photodetection. When multiple comb lines propagate through a dispersive fibre, each optical

frequency accumulates a different phase shift. At the photodetector, which operates as a square-law device, the optical field components beat with one another to produce RF signals. This beating process involves terms of the form $\cos(\omega_1 t) \cdot \cos(\omega_2 t)$, which generate sum and difference frequency components. The difference frequency component corresponds to the desired RF signal; however, the dispersion-induced phase mismatches between the optical tones result in variations in the amplitude of these RF beat notes. In particular, certain frequency components can interfere destructively, leading to fading in the detected RF spectrum. This power fading effect can be periodic and depends on the fibre's dispersion, length, and the frequency spacing of the comb. As a result, careful management of dispersion or spectral shaping is often required to mitigate these impairments and maintain uniform RF signal strength across the comb bandwidth. We experimentally demonstrate the transmission of the Menhir frequency comb over various fibre lengths, with an emphasis on filter optimisation to mitigate the effects of chromatic dispersion, as illustrated in Figure 7-9.

Figure 7-9: Schematic diagram of the experimental setup for optical filter optimization.

Figure 7-10: (a) Comb optical spectra with & without filtering, Detected RF comb after (b) 8 km fiber transmission (c) 22 km fiber transmission with and without optical bandpass filter.

To investigate the influence of optical filtering on transmission performance, the bandwidth of the optical bandpass filter (OBPF) was varied. Post-filtering, the Menhir comb signal was split using a 90:10 optical coupler. Ten percent of the power was directed to an optical power meter for continuous monitoring, while the remaining 90% passed through a variable optical attenuator (VOA) to control launch power and mitigate nonlinear effects. The attenuated signal was then transmitted through single-mode fibre spans of 8 km and 22 km, respectively. Figure 7-10 illustrates the impact of optical filtering on the Menhir comb's RF output spectrum after fibre transmission. Panel (a) shows that the 0.5 nm OBPF confines the optical spectrum to a narrow region around the central wavelength. This optical filtering alters the detected RF spectrum, as shown in panels (b) and (c) for 8 km and 22 km fibre spans, respectively. Without filtering, the broader comb results in more spectral components being transmitted, which are increasingly affected by chromatic dispersion as the fibre length increases. At 8 km, several RF tones remain visible in the unfiltered case, though with reduced power. However, at 22 km, dispersion effects are more severe, and fewer RF tones are detectable without filtering. Applying the OBPF reduces the number of transmitted tones, but also limits the impact of dispersion and nonlinearities, resulting in higher and more stable RF power at both distances.

Figure 7-11 presents the measured signal power and timing jitter of the 2.5 GHz and 25 GHz RF tones as a function of OBPF bandwidth, for fibre spans of 8 km, 13 km, and 22 km. These plots reveal how dispersion and optical filtering jointly influence the temporal coherence and RF stability of comb-based transmission.

2.5 GHz Tone: Signal Power and Jitter

For the 2.5 GHz tone (top row of Figure 7-11), signal power increases steadily with OBPF bandwidth across shorter fibre lengths. In the 8 km case, where dispersion effects are minimal, the power rises almost linearly, reaching ~ 4 dBm at 120 GHz. In contrast, the 22 km case shows a more pronounced saturation and decline beyond ~ 70 GHz, peaking at -13 dBm. This behaviour reflects the onset of chromatic dispersion, which limits coherent accumulation of beat tones beyond a certain spectral range, highlighting the challenges of long-haul transmission without compensation.

Timing jitter follows a complementary trend. At narrow filter bandwidths (20–40 GHz), only a small portion of the OFC is transmitted which leads to fewer beat tones at the photodetector, resulting in poor temporal resolution and elevated jitter. As bandwidth increases toward ~ 60 – 70 GHz, which is the optimal trade off, additional comb lines enhance the signal's harmonic richness, improving temporal resolution and reducing jitter. This range represents an optimal operating point where the RF signal benefits from rich harmonic content without significant dispersion penalties.

Beyond the optimal bandwidth (above ~ 70 GHz), more widely spaced comb lines are included. These lines experience larger differential phase shifts due to chromatic dispersion, which introduces relative delays and phase noise across the comb.

Figure 7-11: Measured signal level and timing jitter for the 2.5 GHz and 25 GHz RF tones as a function of optical bandpass filter (OBPF) bandwidth, for fibre lengths of 8 km, 13 km, and 22 km. Top row: 2.5 GHz tone. Bottom row: 25 GHz tone. Left: signal level. Right: integrated jitter over 1 kHz to 10 MHz.

25 GHz Tone: Signal Power and Jitter

In contrast, the 25 GHz tone (bottom row of Figure 7-11) exhibits significant amplitude ripple across all fibre spans. These fluctuations, caused by destructive interference between non-adjacent comb lines, are more pronounced with increasing fibre length. Signal levels oscillate between -23 dBm and -35 dBm for the 8 km span, -30 dBm to -45 dBm for 13 km. Notably, the 22 km curve consistently shows the lowest signal levels, oscillating between -45 dBm and -57 dBm. Both the amplitude and frequency of these ripples increase with fibre length, reflecting greater accumulated dispersion.

This oscillatory behaviour is characteristic of RF power fading due to interference among pairwise beating comb lines. When the relative phase shift between comb line pairs becomes destructive, such as in the case of a π phase shift, the resulting RF component is significantly attenuated, producing nulls or dips in the detected power. As fibre length increases, so does the amount of accumulated dispersion, which amplifies phase variation across the comb. This leads to more frequent oscillations in power versus bandwidth and deeper fading at specific OBPF settings due to stronger destructive interference.

The timing jitter characteristics of the 25 GHz tone are strongly influenced by signal power fluctuations arising from chromatic dispersion. Phase mismatches between the non-adjacent comb lines that generate the 25 GHz tone lead to destructive interference at certain optical filter bandwidths, resulting in deep fades or nulls in the detected RF power. As the signal approaches these nulls, not only does the amplitude drop significantly, but the RF phase becomes unstable, leading to sharp spikes in timing jitter. This effect is particularly pronounced in the 13 km and 22 km fibre spans, where greater dispersion results in more frequent and deeper signal fading, which is directly mirrored by large jitter excursions.

This sensitivity is further exacerbated by the fact that the 25 GHz tone is formed from beating between comb lines spaced 10 modes apart in the 2.5 GHz Menhir comb. These non-adjacent lines are more susceptible to dispersion-induced phase shifts compared to adjacent lines, which remain relatively phase-coherent over longer distances. As a result, the 25 GHz signal exhibits higher phase noise and reduced timing stability, particularly beyond OBPF bandwidths of 60–70 GHz, where the inclusion of more widely spaced line pairs amplifies dispersion effects. The separation of axes in the corresponding plots reflects the significant differences in jitter magnitude across the tested fibre lengths and filter bandwidths. Ultimately, the combination of power fading and phase noise leads to degraded signal quality and increased timing jitter in high-frequency RF tones under dispersive conditions.

7.4 Clock Phase Caching Techniques

Precise clock phase synchronisation is a fundamental requirement in distributed architectures for 6G communication and sensing systems, particularly where coherent signal processing, accurate localisation, and joint transmission are involved. In such systems, optical fibre links are commonly used to deliver reference signals from a central DU to multiple RUs. However, despite achieving frequency synchronisation through optical frequency combs, the fibre link remains vulnerable to time-varying phase drift caused by temperature and mechanical effects. To address this, clock phase caching has been proposed and demonstrated as a practical and effective method to cancel the residual one-way phase drift. This section introduces the concept of clock phase caching, outlines its advantages, and presents a proof-of-concept implementation, validating its role in maintaining high-precision phase coherence across distributed systems.

7.4.1 Concept and Advantages of Clock Phase Caching

In high-precision distributed systems such as those targeted in 6GMUSICAL, maintaining tight clock phase alignment between DU and RU is essential. While frequency synchronisation may be established using a shared optical frequency comb, a residual phase drift remains due to variations in fibre

propagation delay, particularly from temperature or mechanical changes affecting fibre length.

The propagation delay of an optical fibre depends on both its physical length and refractive index. As temperature changes:

- The length of the fibre slightly increases (thermal expansion),
- The refractive index also varies due to thermo-optic effects.

These effects cause the time-of-flight (ToF) of light through the fibre to change, which in turn causes a change in signal phase. For standard single-mode fibre (SMF-28), the temperature-induced delay variation is approximately:

$$\Delta t \approx 39 \text{ ps/km/C}$$

This means that a 10 km fibre exposed to a 1°C temperature shift will experience nearly 390 ps of additional delay, which corresponds to hundreds of degrees of phase shift at typical GHz carrier frequencies. Even with frequency synchronisation in place, this delay variation results in one-way phase drift, where the clock at the RU appears to drift with respect to the DU due to changing fibre delay in just one direction

Clock phase caching is a technique used to compensate for dynamic one-way phase drift in real time by leveraging the DU's ability to observe two-way fibre delay variations. Figure 7-12 illustrates the principle behind this method in a bidirectional fibre-based synchronisation system. It depicts how fibre-induced phase drift, caused by temperature-dependent changes in the time-of-flight, appears as a measurable two-way phase variation at the DU. By comparing its transmitted and received clocks, the DU estimates the round-trip drift and issues corrective updates to the RU's main and transmit clocks. The figure contrasts the uncompensated scenario (solid lines) with the corrected case using clock phase caching (dashed lines), clearly demonstrating how the technique cancels the one-way phase error. The operation of this mechanism is described in detail below.

Figure 7-12: Illustration of the clock phase caching mechanism. Solid lines show the behaviour without caching; dashed lines show the corrected case with caching applied.

1. Two-way phase comparison at the DU:

The DU continuously monitors the phase difference between its transmitted and received

clock signals over the bidirectional fibre link. Any change in the round-trip propagation delay appears as a measurable phase drift at the DU, measured as $2\varphi(t)$, due to the symmetry of the link.

2. **Clock phase caching and correction:** At regular intervals $1/f_\varphi$, the DU caches this measured drift and applies a correction of $-\varphi(t)$, i.e., half the round-trip drift to compensate for the one-way phase drift experienced by the RU.
3. **Phase adjustments at the RU:** The RU uses this information to adjust both its main clock and Tx clock. The **RU's main clock** is shifted by $-\varphi(t)$ and the RU's Tx clock is shifted by $-2\varphi(t)$, effectively cancelling the accumulated one-way drift and restoring phase alignment with the DU.
4. **Result:**
After correction, the net phase offset is:

$$\varphi(t) - \varphi(t) = 0$$

ensuring that the DU and RU clocks remain phase-synchronized even in the presence of fibre delay fluctuations.

Advantages of clock phase caching include:

- **Compensation for dynamic fibre delay:** Corrects time-varying one-way delay without requiring absolute delay measurement.
- **Preservation of phase coherence:** Enables coherent transmission, distributed beamforming, and high-resolution sensing.
- **Low-overhead and scalable:** Requires only periodic updates rather than continuous correction.
- **Robust implementation:** Operates using standard Tx/Rx phase comparisons and does not require specialized hardware.

7.4.1.1 Implementation of Clock Phase Caching Architecture

Figure 7-13 shows our experimental setup used to investigate the performance of our proposed approach. Limited by the available resources, we only developed one RU. At the DU side, we used a

Figure 7-13: Experimental setup to demonstrate our combined approaches to clock synchronisation in RANs.

Menhir comb with 2.5 GHz f_{rep} and centre frequency 1551.1 nm as the comb source. The Menhir comb features robustness in practical operation environment, compact and ultra-low phase noise that meets the system requirement. We split the comb at the DU, beat the tones on a 5 GHz PD, filter with a 2.5 GHz BPF, amplify, then used a /4 divider to generate a 625 MHz reference clock to synchronise the DU FPGA (field programmable gate array).

The DU FPGA transmitter (Tx) generated real-time 2.5 Gb/s non-return-to-zero (NRZ) on-off-keyed (OOK) packet data containing 2^9 length pseudorandom binary sequences (PRBS-9) sequences and medium access control (MAC) layer information that was modulated onto a 1554.13 nm carrier using an externally modulated laser (EML), attenuated to -19.75 dBm to minimise erbium doped fibre amplifier (EDFA) gain competition with the comb. The second split at the DU passed through an OBPF tuned to 50 GHz to minimise the negative impact of wavelength dispersion fading on the strength of the 25 GHz comb beat tone and its phase noise performance.

The filtered comb, at -10.17 dBm, was combined with the synchronous data from the DU with a 200-GHz-spacing wavelength multiplexer before outbound-only amplification with an EDFA. The combined comb and data then launched at 10.35 dBm into 13 km SSMF. These signals were then demultiplexed by another 200-GHz wavelength demultiplexer. The comb was split by a 50:50 splitter to emulate a two RU system and then recombined with the data (-9.77 dBm) with a coupler. The recombined signals passed through 80 m of feeder fibre, before reception at -7.08 dBm on a 40 GHz PD. The signals were then amplified, split in the RF domain and the 25 GHz RF carrier, 2.5 GHz clock and 2.5 Gb/s data were filtered out with band pass filters (BPF) and a low pass filter (LPF) respectively. The 2.5 GHz clock was divided to 625 MHz with a /4 divider, which synchronised the reference clock of the RU FPGA.

The RU FPGA generated return -1.00 dBm data packets modulated onto a 1555.74 nm carrier which passed through the 13 km SSMF back to the DU before reception by an 18 GHz PD at -17.7 dBm. Clock phase caching was then implemented using the DU FPGA by measuring the $+2\delta\varphi(t)$ shift at its optical-link facing Rx every 0.1 s. Clock phase updates were sent through the optical link to the RU Rx. These updated a phase store which was used to drive a 1st phase interpolator (PI, φ) driving the return RU to DU data transmitter by $-2\delta\varphi(t)$ and a 2nd PI by only $-\delta\varphi(t)$, which drove the RU's main clock. To evaluate how well synchronised the RU was to the DU, this main RU clock drove a <30cm coaxial link (grey) to the DU, the clock phase of which was measured by the DU at a rate of 9.54 kHz.

Figure 7-14: Phase noise measurements of the 25GHz RF carrier and 2.5 GHz clock reflecting very low jitter at RU after optical frequency comb and data reception.

We first investigate the phase noise of the 25 GHz RF carrier and 2.5 GHz clock generated at the RU from the optical frequency comb, as shown in Figure 7-14. For the 25 GHz RF carrier, we show an overall similar jitter (integrated from 1 kHz to 10 MHz) of about 90 fs with and without co-reception

of the data signals, indicating that the data clock tones have negligible impact of the RF carrier phase noise. For the 2.5 GHz clock, we show an overall integrated jitter over the same integration range of 70.3 fs without data. However, with data co-reception, the jitter degrades to 93.1 fs due to noise added from the data signals. The white noise floor in both cases is < -130 dBc/Hz. Figure 7-15 shows the 16-hour long-term stability resulting from running clock phase caching. The red (top) curve shows the DU-measured 2-way clock phase shift of data arriving at the DU from the RU through the optical fibre link, calculated from the phase updates sent to the RU. The blue (bottom) curve shows the RU clock phase synchronised to the DU. The green (middle) curve shows the estimated 1-way shift of the RU’s clock that would have occurred without clock phase caching, calculated by adding half the measured 2-way clock phase offsets to the synchronised RU clock phase offset. The eye diagram inset in Figure 7-16 shows that despite 6.57 dB greater optical clock power than data, the BER of a large proportion of the received eye still remains under 10^{-10} , and we anticipate optimisation of analogue filtering will result in further improvements.

Figure 7-15: 16-hour long-term stability of the RU’s clock phase offset from the DU with clock phase caching.

Figure 7-16: Long-term RU clock phase stability using clock phase caching; inset: error-free data after analogue filtering.

As a comparison against the standard commercial approach of synchronising RUs to the embedded clock in the data from the DU, we also measured the jitter of the 2.5 GHz embedded tone in PRBS-9 data packets generated from the DU FPGA to be 18 ps, over 2 orders of magnitude worse phase noise compared to our approach.

RoF comb clock distribution also provides the basis that allows clock phase caching to be possible. By frequency synchronising the RU using the comb, the clock phase drift is dominated by optical fibre induced clock phase drift.

Finally, Figure 7-16 shows the distribution of the recorded clock phase offset values between the RU and DU: showing 16-hour 6.61 ps RMS wander with clock phase caching, meeting the <30 ps requirement for cm-level positioning.

7.4.1.2 MAC Layer Protocol for Simultaneous Data Transmission and Clock Synchronisation

The data and clock transmission from the DU are kept synchronous by driving the DU FPGA reference clock input with a 625 MHz clock signal generated by dividing the 2.5 GHz tone resulting from beating the entire comb on a 5 GHz photodiode at the DU by a factor of 4 with a digital divider circuit. The reference clock input on the DU FPGA is then multiplied up to 1.25 GHz with an internal FPGA PLL to provide the serial clock that is used to output 2.5 Gb/s data from the DU high speed transmitter that is synchronous to the comb clock. Data for transmission from the DU FPGA is generated in parallel, with all circuitry for this purpose, again synchronous to the comb, driven by a parallel clock generated by dividing the FPGA DU transmitter serial clock by a factor of 32 within the FPGA.

Data sent from the DU to the RU as well as from the RU to the DU is divided into packets with the packet format shown in Figure 7-17 (top). Each packet consists of 2 x PRBS-9 sequences, lasting 410 ns, which are used for error detection, followed by a further 36 bits dedicated for transmission of simplified MAC layer information between the FPGAs and a final partial PRBS-9 payload to pad out the remainder of each packet, lasting 205 ns, followed finally by a 26 ns inter-packet gap. The MAC layer data consists of a 16-bit start of frame delimiter (SFD) for frame alignment at the receiver, a 4 bit packet source address, a 4 bit packet destination address, an 8 bit value containing the relative phase offset (only sent during a phase update), followed by an 8 bit cyclic redundancy check (CRC) generated from the address and phase information. The addresses, relative phases and CRC are encoded using 8B/10B encoding to avoid DC line imbalance.

Figure 7-17: Top: Packet structure with PRBS-9 payloads, MAC header, and inter-packet gap. Bottom: Measured CDR phase tracking using averaged phase updates over 40.96 μs .

Figure 7-18: Serial clock phase adjustment at transmitter and receiver with 6.25 ps resolution.

The one-way change in clock phase offset between the DU and the RU that occurs due to one-way fibre time-of-flight change is compensated indirectly in the following manner: The clock phase offset between the DU local clock and the clock embedded in data arriving at the DU receiver from the RU, which changes due to changes in the two-way time-of-flight in the fibre, is periodically measured using the DU receiver's clock and data recovery circuit at the phase update rate frequency (here: 10 Hz). In each clock phase update, the mean clock phase offset of 2^6 packets arriving at the DU from the RU is first measured, taking 40.96 μs . This mean clock phase offset is then transmitted to the RU from the DU serial transmitter in the MAC layer relative phase offset field of one outgoing packet. Figure 7-18 shows how this measured offset is used to apply phase shifts at the RU using high-resolution interpolator. The RU then corrects the clock phase of packets leaving the RU for transmission to the DU by shifting a clock phase interpolator driving the RU high speed transmitter by the inverse of the relative phase offset measured at the DU. Finally, the RU shifts a second clock phase interpolator driving the main clock of the RU by half the inverse of the relative phase offset measured at the DU. This compensates for the one-way time-of-flight change experienced by the RU's clock.

7.5 Data and Clock Extraction Techniques

In the proposed system architecture, a bank of RF filters is essential to extract specific frequency components from the OFC generated by the Menhir MLL laser. Each comb line corresponds to a stable, phase-coherent RF tone spaced at 2.5 GHz intervals. To support simultaneous data transmission and frequency synchronisation, we require:

- A low-pass filter (LPF) to extract the baseband data signal,
- And a set of band-pass filters (BPFs) to isolate selected RF carrier tones from the comb.

A key requirement is the extraction of the 2.5 GHz tone for clock recovery. This tone serves as the master clock reference and is subsequently divided down for synchronisation and phase caching across RUs. Additionally, other BPFs are needed to isolate higher-frequency comb lines (e.g., 5 GHz, 25 GHz, and 27.5 GHz) for use as RF carriers at each RU. While the tones selected in this implementation are 2.5 GHz, 5 GHz, 25 GHz, and 27.5 GHz, the approach is scalable and any comb line can, in principle, be used as an RF carrier.

As part of this work, we have designed, simulated, and validated the 2.5 GHz and 5 GHz BPFs, which play a critical role in enabling low-jitter clock extraction and stable RF carrier delivery from the distributed optical comb.

7.5.1 Filtering Mechanisms for High Isolation Between Clock and Data Signals

To achieve efficient frequency extraction with minimal interference and high isolation between clock and data channels, two distinct filter technologies were employed based on the target frequency range. Table 5 summarises the filtering technologies at different frequencies.

This hybrid approach ensures optimal performance by leveraging the strengths of each filtering technique.

7.5.2 Design of Data and Clock Extraction Circuits

The design process focused on two key band-pass filters: one centred at 2.5 GHz for clock extraction, and another at 5 GHz to isolate a selected RF carrier. Both filters were implemented using parallel coupled microstrip lines, a widely adopted structure in RF systems due to its compact layout, tunability, and ability to provide sharp passband selectivity with high stopband rejection. Each filter consists of cascaded open-ended microstrip resonators, where the coupling gaps between adjacent lines control the bandwidth, and the line widths influence impedance matching and return loss. These filters were fabricated on standard RF substrates and measured using a vector network analyser.

Table 5: Filtering Technology at different frequencies

Frequency	Function	Filtering Technology
2.5 GHz	Clock extraction	Microstrip Band-Pass Filter
5 GHz	RF carrier for RU	Microstrip Band-Pass Filter
25 GHz	RF carrier for RU	Dielectric Resonator Filter
27.5 GHz	RF carrier for RU	Dielectric Resonator Filter

Figure 7-19(a) presents the measured S21 response of the 2.5 GHz band-pass filter, comparing the custom-designed microstrip filter with a commercially available Mini circuits counterpart. The fabricated filter achieves a centre frequency of 2.5 GHz with an insertion loss of approximately –6.63 dB, while the Mini circuits filter demonstrates a lower loss of –3.73 dB, typical of highly optimised commercial units. Despite the higher loss, the in-house filter shows a much steeper roll-off and stopband attenuation exceeding 50 dB, offering stronger suppression of adjacent tones. This level of selectivity is critical in optical frequency comb systems, where tones are spaced only 2.5 GHz apart and must be cleanly isolated for accurate clock recovery.

Figure 7-19(b) shows the corresponding results for the 5 GHz band-pass filter. The in-house filter exhibits a centre frequency of 5 GHz with an insertion loss of –7.39 dB, compared to –4.48 dB for the Mini circuits filter. Once again, the custom design achieves sharper roll-off and out-of-band attenuation beyond 60 dB, particularly effective at suppressing unwanted spectral components beyond ± 2 GHz from the centre frequency.

These results confirm that while commercial filters generally offer lower insertion loss, the custom-designed microstrip filters deliver markedly better spectral isolation, which is essential for comb-based architectures. Their performance makes them well-suited for high-fidelity data and clock extraction,

where minimal crosstalk and high suppression of adjacent tones are required. Additionally, the microstrip topology supports low-cost fabrication, scalability to multiple channels, and straightforward layout integration into PCB-based RF systems. Together, these benefits make parallel-coupled microstrip filters an attractive and practical solution for the 6G-MUSICAL system.

To extract higher-frequency RF tones—such as the 25 GHz and 27.5 GHz components of the optical frequency comb, dielectric resonator filters (DRFs) are proposed due to their inherently high quality factor (Q), low insertion loss, and compact footprint at millimetre-wave frequencies. These filters are particularly suitable for high-frequency signal selection where microstrip implementations would suffer from increased conductor and dielectric losses. Dielectric resonators, DRs, are made of a ceramic material with a high dielectric constant and are usually cylindrical in shape but can be found in other shapes.

Figure 7-19: Measured S_{21} of the bandpass microstrip filter and a commercially available Mini circuit at (a) 2.5 GHz (b) 5 GHz.

In the case of DRs with a cylindrical shape, their diameter is, in general, approximately equal to

$$D_{DR} \approx \frac{\lambda_0}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}}$$

where λ_0 is the wavelength at the vacuum resonance frequency and ϵ_r is the relative dielectric

constant.

If the dielectric constant of the material that makes up the RD is high, the electric and magnetic fields of a given resonance mode are found confined within and at the periphery of the RD. Therefore, radiation losses are generally small and the quality factor of the DR is basically given by the dielectric losses. For a DR with an $\epsilon_r \geq 30$, the no-load quality factor, Q_u , is approximately equal to the inverse of the dielectric loss factor ($tg \delta$). Typical values of $tg \delta$ used in the realization of RDs range from 1×10^{-3} to 2×10^{-3} , which corresponds to Q_u values greater than 5000.

Currently, by modifying the composition of the material of which the RD is composed, it is possible to change the dependence of the variation of the resonance frequency on temperature. Through this process, it is possible to obtain RDs with temperature coefficients that can vary from -4 ppm/°C to 12 ppm/°C (parts per million per degree Celsius), without a significant change in the quality factor.

Due to the existence of the electromagnetic field at the periphery of the DR, it can be excited or coupled by external microwave circuits. Similar to resonant cavities, the DR can also be excited in an unlimited number of modes. Despite the infinity of possible resonance modes, the most used is the $TE_{01\delta}$ mode, with an electric (E) and magnetic (H) field distribution illustrated in Figure 7-20.

Figure 7-20: Distribution of the electric (E) and magnetic (H) fields in the fundamental mode $TE_{01\delta}$. a) top view; b) side view.

The coupling between the dielectric resonator and the other circuits is done, in fundamental mode, by a magnetic coupling and can be performed by different techniques. In the application under study, aiming at a hybrid implementation in microstrip technology, the DR is magnetically coupled to two microstrip lines in an open circuit as illustrated in Figure 7-21.

Figure 7-21: Structure used for magnetic coupling between the RD and external circuits.

To tune the filter to the desired frequency, the RDs were ground until their resonant frequency was between -5% and 0% of the desired centre frequency. The final tuning is achieved using a metal screw located in the filter cap, as illustrated in Figure 7-22. This procedure enables the adjustment of the

filter's centre frequency without significant degradation in the quality factor, resulting in good thermal stability. In the case of the filter presenting a centre frequency slightly above the desired frequency, it is possible to use a dielectric screw instead of a metal one to reduce this frequency.

Figure 7-22: Tuning the filter to the desired centre frequency.

8 Conclusion

This document presented the initial findings from Task 4.1 and Task 4.2 within WP4 of the 6G-MUSICAL project, which focused on synchronisation mechanisms, algorithms for multistatic sensing, and opto-electronic technologies for precise clock and carrier frequency generation and distribution across network nodes. The work addressed critical challenges in achieving high accuracy, scalability, and cost-effectiveness for next-generation networks.

The proposed framework for the selection of nodes for multistatic introduced Sensing Clustering Interface Manager (SCIM) architecture, which considers factors such as sensing resolution, target type and size, temporal constraints, coverage versus accuracy, redundancy, spatial diversity, bistatic geometry, bandwidth availability, antenna configurations, computational capabilities, and fronthaul capacity. Specifically, a base for the Tx-Rx pairing selection was described, with initial work presented on spatial resolution and bistatic geometry. This included an analysis of the relationship between Tx-Rx locations and corresponding spatial grids with variable spatial resolution.

To enable cooperative sensing, three modes of joint processing—non-coherent, coherent, and hybrid—were explored. Simulation results of radar imaging under various scenarios demonstrated the enhanced performance of joint processing compared to results at receiver nodes.

Two wireless self-synchronisation algorithms were introduced. The first method used channel reciprocity, alternating Tx and Rx roles for bistatic signal matching and employing super-resolution offset estimation (SOE). Simulations confirmed its effectiveness, achieving time synchronisation within 10 picoseconds using a signal bandwidth of 50 MHz. The second method relied on AoA intersection from multiple receiver nodes, operating without direct links, reference timing signals, or angles of departure. It computed mean target locations across receiver nodes and derived time offsets from these means. Numerical simulations validated this method, achieving an accuracy of approximately 1 nanosecond with a bandwidth of 586 MHz.

A unified solution for ps-level clock synchronisation and phase-synchronized RF carrier generation was proposed and experimentally demonstrated. This system employed an ultra-low noise optical frequency comb (OFC) as the master source, specifically using the Menhir femtosecond laser with 2.5 GHz spacing. The comb served as both a clock reference and a generator of multiple RF carriers after photodetection. To avoid traditional bi-directional fibre noise cancellation schemes due to implementation complexity, a clock phase caching technique was employed, effectively compensating for one-way fibre-induced clock phase drift. This is the first known demonstration of combined ps-level clock synchronisation and ultra-low phase noise RF carrier distribution in a unified system, enabling robust, scalable, and cost-effective architectures for next-generation RANs.

These advancements have laid the foundation for addressing synchronisation challenges in 6G-MUSICAL project, supporting high-accuracy positioning, distributed beamforming, and low-jitter carrier distribution. The work demonstrated significant progress in opto-electronic synchronisation technologies, paving the way for enhanced performance and reliability in future wireless systems.

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